

PLATFORM FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Deliverable Code: D6.2

Prepared by: Elisa Tronconi (Astir), Felice Catania (Astir), Stefania Occhipinti (Astir), Giovanni Nattino (IRFMN)

Revised by: Guido Bertolini (IRFMN), Chiara Pandolfini (IRFMN), Giulia Irene Ghilardi (IRFMN)

Version: Final

Date: 27/08/2024

Dissemination level: PUBLIC

Project: eCREAM

enabling Clinical Research in Emergency and Acute care Medicine through automated data extraction

Call: HORIZON-HLTH-2021-TOOL-06

Topic: HORIZON-HLTH-2021-TOOL-06-03

Type of action: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions

Grant Agreement no. 101057726

**Funded by
the European Union**

Summary

Executive Summary 3

Introduction..... 3

Objectives of WP6 4

Report on the platform functional requirements 4

 1. Analysis of the functional requirements 4

 2. Cross components eCREAM Central..... 5

 API Authentication..... 5

 MySQL..... 6

 Translation Manager 6

 3. Cross components of Local eCREAM 6

 eCREAM Hospital Client..... 6

 Anonymization tool 6

 MySQL..... 6

 Normalisation tool..... 7

 4. NLP–DeVal study 7

 5. UC1 study flow..... 8

 NLP tool 9

 Calculation of propensity to hospitalisation..... 9

 New ED-EHR..... 10

 MIP interface 11

 6. UC2 study flow..... 11

 New ED-EHR..... 12

 7. Security measures and non-functional requirements..... 12

 Infrastructure requirements..... 12

 Functional requirements 13

 8. Design and development of the eCREAM Translation Manager..... 13

 9. Design of the platform architecture..... 14

 10. Installation of the platform infrastructure and modules 15

Innovation beyond the state-of-the-art of the technical developments 15

Conclusion on the platform functional requirements..... 16

Annexes 16

Executive Summary

This document outlines the progress in developing the eCREAM integrated platform under Work Package 6 (WP6). The primary goal of WP6 is to create a unified platform that integrates various eCREAM modules, including interfaces with hospitals, natural language processing (NLP), semantic transformation, translations, and data analysis. The platform will also ensure consistency in localizing eCREAM tools across different countries, functioning as a central hub for all project activities.

Key achievements in WP6 include the design of the platform's architecture and the establishment of the necessary infrastructure for its implementation. A major component, the Translation Manager (TM), has been developed and deployed to manage translations across the consortium languages, ensuring accurate localization of all user-facing elements. The TM is integrated with the platform's other modules and provides automated translation support, enhancing efficiency.

The platform's functional requirements have been carefully analysed, focusing on two main components: the Local eCREAM, installed at hospitals for data extraction and preprocessing, and the Central eCREAM, which stores and organizes data for further analysis and use in specific studies. Critical cross-cutting components like secure API authentication, data management using MySQL, and the integration of NLP tools have been developed to support the platform's objectives.

Security and scalability have been prioritized, with the platform hosted on AWS cloud infrastructure, certified for data protection. Ongoing tasks include finalizing platform infrastructure, deploying key modules, and setting the stage for the full operational rollout of the eCREAM integrated platform.

Overall, WP6 is progressing as planned, with significant advancements in both the design and technical development of the eCREAM platform, laying a strong foundation for future project phases.

Introduction

The primary objective of WP6 is to develop the eCREAM integrated platform. This platform will act as a central hub, connecting all the eCREAM modules, including interfaces with hospitals, natural language processing (NLP), semantic transformation, translations, and data analysis. Additionally, it will ensure consistency in the localization of eCREAM tools across the various participating countries, functioning as a unified information system.

This document presents the progress made in designing the architecture of the integrated eCREAM platform and establishing the necessary infrastructure for its implementation. It begins with an overview of the current state of the art and the goals for this work package. This is followed by an in-depth analysis of Task 6.1, which focuses on identifying the functional requirements of the platform, developed in collaboration with project partners, and Task 6.2, which covers the design and development of the eCREAM Translation Manager. The Translation Manager (TM) is a key system that will enable consortium members to manage translations across the different project languages, ensuring that all the terms required for the modules that provide an interface with end-users are accurately localized.

The document also includes a summary of tasks 6.3, which details the design of the platform architecture, and 6.4, which covers the installation of the platform infrastructure and modules.

Objectives of WP6

WP6 is dedicated to developing a transversal module that ensures the alignment of all translations necessary for localizing various eCREAM tools across participating countries. Additionally, WP6 integrates all the eCREAM modules (interfaces with hospitals, NLP, semantic transformation, translations, and data analysis) into a coherent information system.

Specifically, WP6 aims to:

- Develop the Translation Manager to function across all eCREAM modules
- Design the architecture of the eCREAM integrated platform
- Provide the infrastructure required for implementation
- Implement internal interfaces.

Report on the platform functional requirements

1. Analysis of the functional requirements

This document outlines the overall functionality of the eCREAM platform, which is divided into two components: Local and Central.

- **eCREAM Local:** installed at hospitals, it collects and extracts variables from hospital data systems to build the eCREAM model. It also manages data preprocessing and transmission to the Central eCREAM component
- **eCREAM Central:** it organises and stores data in two distinct database schemas dedicated to the Use Case 1 (UC1) and Use Case 2 (UC2). UC1 focuses on developing models to calculate the propensity for hospitalisation, while UC2 aims to develop dashboards for citizens, ED staff, and policymakers.

The functional analysis was informed by the needs of the UC1, UC2, and NLP-DeVal studies, the latter being focused on NLP tool development and validation to enable clinical research in emergency medicine. This analysis is structured around the study protocols and the cross-cutting components used in the platform.

The following diagram summarises the modules installed in the Local and Central components of the eCREAM platform described in detail in D2.2.

To enhance readability, the functional aspects of the eCREAM platform were described by detailing each of the three eCREAM studies, while also covering the transversal components involved in each scenario (NLP-DeVal, UC1 and UC2). The diagram below provides an overview of the functional aspects of Use Cases 1 and 2, with the hospital depicted as the source of data, acquired through the integration interfaces.

2. Cross components eCREAM Central

The three protocols require several specific key modules, which are detailed below.

API Authentication

Based on T6.3 principles, the functional design intended to decouple the application modules. Specifically, a dedicated module was implemented for authentication.

Secure authentication between the Local and Central components of the eCREAM platform is achieved through the HMAC (Hash-based Message Authentication Code) protocol for API calls. The eCREAM Hospital Client services do not transmit any password over the encrypted channel, only the (potentially public) identifying data item 'clientId'.

HMAC is an authentication mechanism that uses a hash function together with a secret key. This protocol ensures both the message's integrity and its source's authenticity. In summary, HMAC offers an excellent compromise between security and efficiency. The following advantages dictated the choice of this protocol:

- **Message Integrity:** HMAC guarantees that the message is not altered during transfer. Any modification to the message after the HMAC application will be detected since the hash will no longer match
- **Source Authenticity:** Using a secret key, HMAC ensures that the message comes from the declared source. Only those who possess the secret key can generate a valid HMAC
- **Efficiency:** HMAC is based on cryptographic hash functions such as SHA-256, which are fast to calculate and implement, making the authentication phase quick
- **Security:** The security of HMAC depends on the robustness of the hash function used and the secrecy of the key. Even if an attacker knows the message, they cannot generate a valid HMAC for a new message without knowing the key
- **Versatility:** HMAC can be used with different cryptographic hash functions (such as SHA-256, SHA-1, MD5), making it adaptable to various levels of security and performance
- **Interoperability:** HMAC is a standardised and widely supported algorithm, ensuring interoperability between different implementations and platforms.

MySQL

The management and organisation of data are entrusted to the MySQL relational database. In particular:

- **Data Management:** Data will be stored in structured tables, making it organised, accessible, and securely updatable
- **Data Integrity:** MySQL supports various constraints (primary keys, foreign keys, uniqueness, etc.) to ensure data accuracy and consistency. It uses transactions to ensure that multiple operations on the data are either successfully completed or entirely undone in the event of an error
- **Security:** MySQL employs user and permission management to control access and the operations that can be performed. It also supports data encryption to protect the information it contains
- **Performance and Scalability:** MySQL utilises tools to optimise SQL queries, enhancing the speed of data retrieval and updates, even when handling large volumes
- **Backup:** MySQL provides tools to ensure that data copies exist for recovery in case of loss or damage, allowing for the reliable restoration of the initial state.

Translation Manager

The TM is a component used in UC1 and UC2. It is set up on the eCREAM central platform and supplies and updates the translations of the textual expressions used by all platform modules.

The application modules interact with the TM in different use cases to obtain translations of all relevant elements from English (the default language) into the different languages of the consortium.

The TM platform's communication interfaces and technical specifications are described in the attached files. The Translation Manager module was developed and released in Central eCREAM and can be accessed at translation.ecreamproject.eu.

Please refer to the content of 'Design and development of the eCREAM Translation Manager' for details on the component.

3. Cross components of Local eCREAM

The Local eCREAM platform comprises specific modules to support the different protocols.

eCREAM Hospital Client

The eCREAM Hospital Client is a component of the Local eCREAM platform that acts as a link between the hospital, where data extraction takes place, and the Central eCREAM component, where the data are sent. In the Local component, the data will be aggregated, pre-processed, and rendered in accordance with the eCREAM model.

The description of the component can be found in D2.2 under "eCREAM Hospital Client - Integration job manager".

Anonymization tool

This tool is a market product that performs a text anonymization function. It analyses text to identify, classify, and mask text portions containing personally identifiable information.

MySQL

The relational database MySQL also performs data management and organization locally.

Normalisation tool

The collected data will be locally standardised through a dedicated normalisation and transcoding component in Local eCREAM. The structured information extracted from the data collected from the various hospital records may have different units and formats.

These differences can occur both within the same hospital – where a result may change due to the use of a different unit of measurement over time (e.g., change of reagents in the analysis laboratory and reference scales for measuring specific clinical parameters) – and between different hospitals in the same country or other countries. This situation can occur in UC1, for example.

On the other hand, for UC2, some hospitals might use 4-level and others 5-level priority coding at the triage; again, a normalisation process must be applied to make information comparable.

4. NLP–DeVal study

As described in D2.2, the application components involved in this use case are listed below.

In this case, all activities necessary for the transfer of data to the NLP server will be prepared locally.

The NLP De-Val protocol needs an eCREAM Hospital client module in the local eCREAM platform.

The eCREAM Hospital client component will retrieve textual notes, ensuring they are not traceable to the patient. This will be done through the Integration Job Manager application component, which will interact with a component designed to remove any possible biographical references from the texts. The anonymized data will then be sent to the NLP Server via the NLP Integrator component.

5. UC1 study flow

In UC1, local processing at each hospital calculates indicators that can predict the EDs’ propensity for hospitalisation.

As also described in D2.2, the application components involved in this use case are listed below.

In the following diagram, the functional modules are described.

The UC1 protocol needs specific modules on the local eCREAM platform.

In the eCREAM Hospital Client, data retrieved from hospitals undergoes anonymization. After this process, the data are sent to the NLP tool via the eCREAM Center Integration application module. The details of this module are described in D2.2.

NLP tool

The data received from the individual hospitals and collected in the eCREAM base model should be processed to identify patients with dyspnoea and TLoC (transient loss of consciousness).

The collected data are submitted to the NLP component, which was previously trained in NLP-DeVal, and installed in the central platform. The NLP is invoked at two different times:

- at first, the triage notes and diagnosis data are sent to NLP to process and interpret them, returning only the eligible cases involving patients with dyspnoea and TLoC;
- after filtering the data, the unstructured textual information related to these cases is sent to transform it into structured information that will feed the local database with the variables collected in the CRF, i.e., the collection of variables identified by eCREAM as important for predicting the hospitalisation of patients with dyspnoea or TLoC.

The NLP tool module operates based on the training and insights gained during the NLP-DeVal phase.

The data are then processed by the local encoding normalisation module described in the cross components. The module will return pre-processed data to be sent to the Central eCREAM platform.

Calculation of propensity to hospitalisation

The 'UC1 Modules - R' component is being designed and contributes to the realisation of WP4 and, in particular, of 'Use case 1 - Analysis of the disposition decision to hospitalise a patient from the ED'.

The UC1 Modules - R component is delivered from the central platform.

UC1 relies on a statistical model estimating the probability of hospitalisation from the ED. The key parameters to be fed into the model were identified in WP4 and formally defined in WP2. The central eCREAM platform will collect the normalised information from the participating hospitals, and the centralised data will be used for the analyses, which will involve three main steps:

1. **Data preprocessing and generation of the analytic dataset.** The data will be sourced directly from the central eCREAM platform, and exploratory data analysis will be performed to assess the consistency of the data for the purposes of UC1. The data will be provided in csv or similar R data format. Variables will undergo the transformations required for the statistical modelling, and an analytic dataset with the pre-processed data will be created and stored in the central eCREAM platform.
2. **Development of the statistical model.** The analytic dataset will be used to develop the statistical model estimating the probability of hospitalisation. Based on preliminary considerations on the sparsity of the data in the existing EHRs and the expected heterogeneity of the predictive weight of several factors (see UC1 Study Protocol, T4.1 – Drafting the protocol of Use Case 1 study), decision tree algorithms will be primarily considered for the development of the statistical model. However, to generate a benchmark on the performance of the developed model, the use of a family of different algorithms will be explored too, spanning from traditional regression to other machine learning methods. The models will be compared in terms of calibration and discrimination. The output of this step will be a sophisticated algorithm producing an estimate of the probability of hospitalisation based on the values of the parameters (or, likely, a subset of the parameters) imported from the hospitals.

- 3. Production of centre-specific reports.** The model will then be used to estimate the probability on all patients in the analytic database. For each centre, the expected number of hospitalised patients, computed as the sum of the estimated probabilities, will be compared to the observed number of hospitalizations. The comparison of expected and observed hospitalizations will provide information on the performance of the centre (hospitalisation rate higher than/lower than/equal to the average of the participating EDs). A template of a centre-specific report will be generated, which will be centred around the comparison of expected vs. observed hospitalisation rates. The report produced will include summary statistics, figures, and tables describing the factors that will be identified as relevant to affect the probability of hospitalisation and possibly explain differences in the performances of the different EDs. The template will be used to produce reports for all the centres.

All analyses will be performed using R in the ‘UC1 Modules – R’. R is open-source software for data wrangling, analysis, and visualisation. The available libraries facilitate the interface of the software with relational and nonrelational databases, the manipulation of large sets of information in different formats, and the development of advanced statistical models. Furthermore, its integration in Notebooks and Markdown documents will be leveraged for the construction of the template for the centre-specific reports, which will then be used to generate the reports for all the participating centres.

New ED-EHR

Design and development activities related to the new ED-EHR are ongoing in WP3. The eCREAM ED-EHR will be released in a DEMO version and a version released for the hospital facilities in Crete, deployed in two different contexts. The DEMO version will be deployed in the infrastructure of eCREAM, while the second will be deployed in the infrastructure of the hospital that will adopt the new ED patient file.

Regardless of the deployment context, the new ED-EHR will require the Translation Manager (TM) to provide all translated labels. This ensures that in both the DEMO configuration and the hospital environment, the labels and user interfaces are fully translated and localised according to the specific needs of the deployment.

Specifications for the authentication of the ED-EHRs with the central eCREAM platform are being defined. Similarly, how data will be communicated to the UC1 DB is being analysed. The ED-EHR folder will expose FHIR resources based on the UC1 use case flow. Data will be collected with a frequency to be determined.

MIP interface

The extracted data in MIP-compatible format will feed two datasets for CHUV:

- **MIP**, containing all clinical data collected in UC1 and reserved for authorised researchers
- **Public MIP**, containing basic data derived from a selection of data collected and intended for the MIP.

The dataset provided to the MIP will be generated from the ‘analytical’ dataset, which results from initial preprocessing to provide a dataset ready for analysis. MIP will apply further pseudonymization checks on this data.

The data provided on a one-off basis will have the following formats:

- Dataset in standard format (e.g., CSV)
- Dictionary (data model) prepared in CSV or JSON format, containing the variables in use, with details on the type of data (quantitative, categorical, binary), possible values, and definitions for each variable.

6. UC2 study flow

As described in D2.2, the application components involved in this use case are listed below.

The UC2 protocol needs two main modules on the local eCREAM platform:

1. **Normalization Module:** This module, described among the cross components, is used by both the UC1 and UC2 protocols
2. **Meta-Indicator Processing:** In the eCREAM Hospital Client, normalised data are collected and pre-processed to produce anonymized intermediate data. These data are then used to calculate various indicators, including the calculation of overcrowding.

The UC2 protocol also needs four main functional modules installed within the central eCREAM platform:

1. A web-based application providing the following functionalities:
 - A dashboard dedicated to ED operators for real-time monitoring of statistical and predictive indicators, helping them stay aware of logistical and epidemiological critical phenomena, current or upcoming, that could affect their own ED. Integrated within the central eCREAM platform, this dashboard is intended to process data collected from multiple EDs within the same region, enabling the calculation of indicators that cannot be derived from the data of a single ED alone
 - A web-based dashboard dedicated to the governance operators for the monitoring of statistical indicators, helping them understand logistical and epidemiological phenomena, past, current or upcoming, that affect the region and the healthcare service they manage
 - An administrative dashboard will allow the system administrators to set up the ED structural information and manage the provisioning of the end-user accounts
 - A module for users' authentication. This module will have to provide access security and authorization controls.
1. A web application intended to provide citizens with real-time information about the ED services of their region
2. A web service interface that will provide the mobile application with the data to be shown to the citizens
3. A back-end data processing module that will calculate the indicators to be shown within the dashboards and the mobile application. This module will process the data collected in the UC2 database schema.

The functional and technical specifications of these modules are in progress.

New ED-EHR

The New ED EHR module is the same component described in paragraph UC1 study flow.

7. Security measures and non-functional requirements

Particular attention was paid to analysing the specific requirements to meet the security and data protection issues, along with the GDPR principles such as data access minimisation, data anonymization or pseudonymization, and privacy by design and by default.

Other issues concern service continuity and infrastructure scalability.

Some issues are dealt with by infrastructure requirements, and others mainly by functional requirements.

Infrastructure requirements

- The Central eCREAM platform is hosted in the AWS cloud infrastructure, based in the Milan area. This cloud solution ensures easy infrastructure scalability, high availability, and functionalities, allowing quick service recovery in case of critical damage

- AWS cloud service is certified according to the standard ISO/IEC 27018:2019, a code of practice that focuses on protecting personal data in the cloud
- Scanning of systems (using Checkmarx SCA software and IntelliJ plug-ins) to identify vulnerabilities on a quarterly basis by providing lists of vulnerabilities prioritised based on severity
- The exposure of the local eCREAM system on the Internet and the APIs that realise the data flows from the local application to the central eCREAM platform take place via HTTPS protocol that implements encryption on data transport and presentation
- All web applications and APIs are securely exposed on the Internet via HTTPS, granting the encryption of all the transmitted data
- Secure authentication between the local and central application components of the eCREAM platform is done through the Hash-based Message Authentication Code (HMAC) protocol for authenticating API calls. HMAC is an authentication mechanism that uses a hash function together with a secret key
- A VPN is set to limit access to the local eCREAM component only to authorised and registered users.

Functional requirements

- Data minimisation:
 - the collection of data from the hospitals is limited to the information strictly needed by the use cases;
 - the access to data by the web applications or the APIs is managed according to the user's role, which reflects the need for the designed workflow
- Anonymization and pseudonymization measures for data extracted from the emergency room and other hospital records will be processed by applying
 - For the NLP-DeVal and UC2 protocols: anonymization or removal of identifying information from the data so that the individual can no longer be identified
 - for UC1 protocol: pseudonymization
- The system implements the event logging, and all the data accesses by applications and users are tracked in the application log. The events registry is monitored
- The user passwords are managed respecting the following complexity:
 - At least 8 characters
 - At least one uppercase character
 - At least one lowercase character
 - At least one numeric character
 - At least one special character among the following: ! £ \$ % & / \ < > () = ? ^ _ + * . : ; ' @ #
 - Maximum two consecutive identical characters
 - The last two passwords used cannot be set

8. Design and development of the eCREAM Translation Manager

A second major release of the Translation Manager was completed, tested, and delivered, with user accounts provided to key Italian participants. The functionalities related to Key Management (KM) were improved, including the ability to add keys either individually or in bulk, manage keys, and search and translate keys. The automatic integration with the DeepL internet service was developed and established, and the Translation Management module was completed. Additionally, the API that allows the application to automatically receive language localization was finalized.

PLATFORM FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

The main workflow involving KM begins when an eCREAM software developer requests a key for a text element that needs to be included in the software. KM searches for an existing key in the Key Database. If a matching key exists, KM provides it; otherwise, a new key is created. After creating the key, the Key Management Application (KMA) notifies the translators and provides the key to the API. The eCREAM software can then receive the bundle with the default version (in English), which will be updated after the key is translated.

Documentation activities were also completed, resulting in a specification document and a user manual (which will be added as an annexes). A training plan for using the TM platform was established, consisting of:

- Thematic videos (focused on specific functionalities) in Italian and English, explaining the functioning of different pages of the TM platform and their navigation from the user's perspective.
- A summary presentation indexing the training videos.

To ensure effective training for TM platform users, the training videos and associated PowerPoint presentations will be available in a dedicated space for users.

The development activities of the TM platform's web application, which were required as part of the objectives of Task 6.2, can be considered globally completed.

AWS was chosen as the eCREAM delivery platform, and with reference to the application component, an IP address was defined, and a URL assigned at [https:// translation.ecreamproject.eu/](https://translation.ecreamproject.eu/).

The "eCREAM Structural Questionnaire" application will be the first to be configured in production with the text expressions entered and validated in English, Italian, and Greek. Below is a screenshot of the TM platform's homepage:

Application	Keys(#)	Values(#)	Italian	Slovenian	Slovak	Polish	Greek
ED EHR	47	54	25%	3%	59%	1%	3%
Dashboard	469	479	2%	0%	4%	0%	0%
Citizens mobile app	15	20	35%	5%	45%	0%	15%
Statistical analysis platform	30	35	40%	0%	22%	0%	31%
Citizens backend Service	466	474	6%	1%	7%	0%	1%
Mario Negri TEST	319	328	5%	0%	0%	0%	0%
FBK Test	9	9	0%	0%	11%	0%	0%

9. Design of the platform architecture

T6.3 is scheduled to start in M25. The definition of functional requirements is closely linked to the platform's architecture, which influences and precedes this task. Although tasks 6.1 and 6.3 are managed separately, they are designed with a unified approach to ensure that the principles of T6.3 guide the development of functional requirements.

These guiding principles have separated the architecture's functionalities, making the application modules independent and easier to scale.

Different application modules need to integrate with external systems or services, requiring clear internal and external interfaces to ensure smooth and secure communication. For example, the Authentication Module, described in the 'Analysis of the Functional Requirements' section, follows this approach.

10. Installation of the platform infrastructure and modules

The activities for this task were scheduled from M37 to M42, starting in September 2025, but have already begun. A contract with AWS (certified according to the ISO 27018 protocol) has been established for the eCREAM delivery component.

Innovation beyond the state-of-the-art of the technical developments

The eCREAM integrated platform represents a significant advancement beyond the current state-of-the-art in several key areas, including modular integration, data localization, and multi-language support. These innovations address existing limitations in healthcare data management, especially in multi-country and multi-language contexts, where seamless integration and localization of tools are critical.

- **Modular integration and interoperability:** One of the primary innovations of the eCREAM platform is its ability to integrate various specialized modules - such as NLP, semantic transformation, translations, and data analysis - into a unified, coherent system. The architecture of the eCREAM platform allows for the decoupling of application modules, enhancing flexibility and scalability. This modular approach is facilitated by secure API-based communication using HMAC protocol, which ensures that each module can operate independently while still contributing to the overall system functionality. This level of modular integration is a significant improvement over existing platforms, which often face challenges in maintaining system coherence when integrating multiple, disparate components.
- **Advanced translation management and localization:** The TM is a cutting-edge tool that addresses the complex needs of multi-language support in healthcare systems. Unlike traditional systems that rely on static translations, the TM allows for dynamic, real-time management of translations across various languages used in the consortium. This ensures that all terms and expressions used in the platform's interfaces are accurately localized, a critical requirement in the healthcare domain, where precise communication is essential. The integration of TM with DeepL, a leading machine translation service, further enhances the platform's ability to provide high-quality translations swiftly, a capability not commonly found in current systems.
- **Secure and efficient data handling:** The eCREAM platform also introduces innovations in data security and efficiency. The use of the HMAC protocol for secure API communication and the implementation of MySQL for robust data management ensures that data integrity, security, and accessibility are maintained at all times. Furthermore, the platform's data handling processes are designed to comply with GDPR principles, including data minimisation, anonymization, and pseudonymization, ensuring that sensitive patient data is protected. This level of data security and compliance with international standards surpasses many existing systems that may not fully address these critical concerns.
- **Integration of NLP:** The integration of advanced Natural Language Processing (NLP) tools within the eCREAM platform represents a significant leap forward to obtain useful data. The NLP tools are designed to extract and process unstructured data from clinical notes, transforming it into structured data that can be used for analysis and predictive modelling. This capability is particularly innovative in the context

of emergency medicine, where timely and accurate interpretation of clinical data can have a profound impact on patient outcomes.

- Scalability and cloud-based infrastructure: The choice of AWS cloud infrastructure for hosting the Central eCREAM platform offers significant advantages in terms of scalability, availability, and disaster recovery. The platform’s ability to scale its infrastructure quickly and efficiently to meet the demands of multiple participating countries is a noteworthy advancement. Additionally, the use of a certified cloud service that adheres to ISO/IEC 27018:2019 standards ensures that the platform not only meets, but exceeds, current best practices in data protection and cloud security.

In conclusion, the eCREAM integrated platform embodies several innovative advancements: by addressing critical challenges such as modular integration, multi-language localisation, data security, and the application of NLP, eCREAM sets a new benchmark for future developments in this field.

Conclusion on the platform functional requirements

It is important to underline that deliverables D2.2 and D6.2, although referring to work packages with different objectives, have strongly interconnected objectives.

The ‘eCREAM integrated platform’ WP is subdivided into 6 tasks. In compiling D6.2, particularly in relation to T6.1, it was necessary to address certain aspects related to the general design of the infrastructure and installation.

For example, the release of the TM component on the Central eCREAM platform involves considerations pertaining to tasks 6.3 and 6.4, which have later start-up times.

The following is a summary mirror of WP6 for a better reading of the above.

WP	Task	Year 2				Year 3				Year 4			
		T1- 2	T2- 2	T3- 2	T4- 2	T1- 3	T2- 3	T3- 3	T4- 3	T1- 4	T2- 4	T3- 4	T4- 4
6	T6.1 Functional requirements												
6	T6.2 Translation Manager												
6	T6.3 Platform architecture												
6	T6.4 Installation of the Platform												

Annexes

Annex 1_D62 - eCREAM Functional Specification Translation Manager

Annex 2_D62 - eCREAM User Manual Translation Manager

Annex 1

Functional Specifications

TRANSLATION MANAGER

Project: eCREAM

enabling Clinical Research in Emergency and Acute care Medicine through automated data extraction

Call: HORIZON-HLTH-2021-TOOL-06

Topic: HORIZON-HLTH-2021-TOOL-06-03

Type of action: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions

Grant Agreement no. 101057726

INDEX

1.	INTRODUCTION.....	7
1.1	Scope.....	7
2.	Definitions, acronyms e abbreviations	8
2.1	Modules catalogue.....	8
3.	API.....	10
3.1	List of keys associated with the individual application.....	10
3.2	List of keys associated with the individual application module.....	11
3.3	List of keys associated with the individual application element.....	12
3.4	Bundle model	12
4.	ACTORS' MODEL	14
4.1	Catalogue of the actors.....	14
4.2	Hierarchy among actors.....	14
4.3	Main flow	15
5.	CATALOGUE OF USE CASES.....	17
5.1	Use case Access to TM	17
5.1.1	Access to TM	17
5.1.2	Access to TM – Scope.....	17
5.1.3	Access to TM – Security and confidentiality requirements	17
5.1.4	Access to TM – Main flow	17
5.1.5	Access to TM – Information covered	18
5.1.6	Access to TM – User interface.....	18
5.2	Use case Home view	19
5.2.1	Home TM – Roles.....	19
5.2.2	Home TM – Scope	19
5.2.3	Home TM – Security and confidentiality requirements.....	19
5.2.4	Home TM – Main flow.....	19
5.2.5	Home TM – Information covered.....	20
5.2.6	Home TM – User Interface.....	20
5.3	Use case Menu TM view	24
5.3.1	Menu TM - Roles	24
5.3.2	Menu TM – Scope	24
5.3.3	Menu TM – Security and confidentiality requirements.....	24

5.3.4	Menu TM – Main flow.....	24
5.3.5	Menu TM – Information covered.....	25
5.3.6	Menu TM – User interface	25
5.4	Use case “Add Key” management.....	28
5.4.1	Use case “Add key” roles management.....	28
5.4.2	Add key – Scope	28
5.4.3	Add key – Security and confidentiality requirements.....	28
5.4.4	Add key – Main flow.....	29
5.4.5	Add key – Information covered.....	29
5.4.6	Add key – User Interface	31
5.5	Use case - Single Key Entry Management.....	32
5.5.1	Single key entry - Roles	32
5.5.2	Single key entry – Scope.....	32
5.5.3	Single key entry – Security and confidentiality requirements	32
5.5.4	Single key entry – Main flow	33
5.5.5	Single key entry – Information covered	33
5.5.6	Single Key Entry – User Interface	33
5.6	Use Case Management Massive input through excel file.....	37
5.6.1	Massive input through excel file – Roles.....	37
5.6.2	Massive input via excel file – Scope.....	37
5.6.3	Massive input via excel file - Security and confidentiality requirements	37
5.6.4	Massive input via excel file - Main Flow	37
5.6.5	Massive input via excel file - Information processed.....	38
5.6.6	Massive input via excel file - User interface	38
5.7	Use case - Manage Tasks.....	46
5.7.1	Tasks -Roles	46
5.7.2	Tasks - Scope	46
5.7.3	Tasks – Requisiti di sicurezza e riservatezza	46
5.7.4	Tasks – Main flow.....	46
5.7.5	Tasks – Information covered.....	47
5.7.6	Tasks – User interface	47
5.8	Use case Manage “Manage Keys”	49
5.8.1	Manage keys – Roles.....	49

5.8.2	Manage keys – Scope	49
5.8.3	Manage keys – Security and confidentiality requirements	49
5.8.4	Manage keys – Main flow	49
5.8.5	Manage key – Information covered	50
5.8.6	Manage key – User Interface	50
5.9	Use case manage “Searching”	52
5.9.1	Searching – Roles	52
5.9.2	Searching – Scope	52
5.9.3	Searching – Security and confidentiality requirements	52
5.9.4	Searching – Main flow	52
5.9.5	Searching – Information covered	53
5.9.6	Searching – User interface	53
5.10	Use case manage “Editing key”	54
5.10.1	Editing key – Roles	54
5.10.2	Editing key – Scope	55
5.10.3	Editing key – Security and confidentiality requirements	55
5.10.4	Editing key – Main flow	55
5.10.5	Editing key – Information covered	56
5.10.6	Editing key – User interface	58
5.11	Use case manage Translate	60
5.11.1	Translate – Roles	60
5.11.2	Translate – Scope	60
5.11.3	Translate – Security and confidentiality requirements	60
5.11.4	Translate – Main flow	61
5.11.5	Translate – Information covered	61
5.11.6	Translate – user interface	61
5.12	Manage “Translate” – Admin/Translator	62
5.12.1	Manage “Translate” – Validated value	63
5.12.2	Manage “Translate” – Not validated value	66
5.12.3	Manage “Translate” – Not translated value	69

List of Figures

Figure 1– Architecture diagram.....	8
Figure 2 – Workflow sequence of the different modules	9
Figure 3– Actors involved in TM.....	15
Figure 4 - Use Case diagram	16
Figure 5– Key management workflow.....	16
Figure 6 - Use case Access to TM.....	17
Figure 7 – Interface use case Access to TM.....	18
Figure 8– Use case Home TM	19
Figure 9 – Interface use case Home TM – Admin.....	21
Figure 10 – Json Interface.....	22
Figure 11 – Interface use case Home TM – Translator SL - SK	23
Figure 12 – Interface use case Home TM – Translator IT.....	23
Figure 13 – Use case Menu TM	24
Figure 14 – Interface use case Menu of first level TM – Admin.....	25
Figure 15 – Interface use case Menu of second level TM - Admin.....	25
Figure 16 – Interface use case Menu of first level TM – Translator	25
Figure 17 - Interface menu – Admin.....	26
Figure 18 – Interface menu – Translator	26
Figure 19 – Interface menu	26
Figure 20 – Interface About TM	26
Figure 21 – Use case Add key roles management.....	28
Figure 22 – Use case interface - Add key.....	31
Figure 23 – Use case Single Key Entry Management.....	32
Figure 24 – Use case Interface Add key – Insert key	34
Figure 25 - – Case Use Interface Add key – Insert key - Ontologies.....	35
Figure 26 – Use case Interface Add key – Insert key - Ontologies	35
Figure 27 – Use case Interface Add key – Insert key – Mandatory fields.....	36
Figure 28 – Add key – existed key	36
Figure 29 – Use case Massive input Management.....	37
Figure 30 – Use case Interface - Add key – massive entry menu	39
Figure 31 – Use case Interface Add key – massive entry - Insert from file	39
Figure 32 – Use case interface Add key – massive entry - Download template	39
Figure 33 – Use case interface Add key – Massive input, Insert from file – Open file	40
Figure 34 – Use case Interface Add key – massive input – download file.....	40
Figure 35 – Use case interface Add key – Massive entry - File to upload	42
Figure 36 – Use case interface Add key – Massive entry - Import	42
Figure 37 – Use case Interface Add key – Massive input - Entered task progress	43
Figure 38 – Use case Interface Add key – Massive input - download file	43
Figure 39 – Use case Interface Add key – Massive entry– Import keys from file	44
Figure 40 – Use case Manage Tasks	46
Figure 41 – Use case interface Add key – Tasks	47
Figure 42 – Use case interface Add key – Import Tasks	48
Figure 43 – Use case manage Manage keys	49

Figure 44 – Use case manage Manage keys menu.....	50
Figure 45 – Use case manage Manage keys interface.....	51
Figure 46 – Use case Manage keys - Searching	52
Figure 47 – Use case Searching interface	53
Figure 48 – Use case Searching search and reset function keys	54
Figure 49 – Use case Searching - fields.....	54
Figure 50 – use case manage Editing key	55
Figure 51 – use case interface Manage - Editing key	58
Figure 52 – use case interface Editing key.....	59
Figure 53 – use case manage Translate.....	60
Figure 54 – use case Translate - menu	60
Figure 55 – Use case Translate – ADMIN.....	62
Figure 56 – Use case Translate - Validate value	63
Figure 57 – use case Translate - Filter	63
Figure 58 – Use case Translate – filter mask	64
Figure 59 – use case Translate - searching filter	64
Figure 60 – use case Translate - edit translation.....	65
Figure 61 – Use case Translate - list of translated and non-validated values	66
Figure 62 – use case Translate - Filter (non-validated)	67
Figure 63 – Use case Translate - operations.....	67
Figure 64 – Use case Translate - edit translation	68
Figure 65 - Manage case Translate – not translated values.....	69
Figure 66 – Use case Translate - filter (not translated values).....	69
Figure 67 – use case Translate - operations.....	70
Figure 68 – Use case Translate - edit translation	70

1. INTRODUCTION

All modules developed within eCREAM that provide an interface for end users must be localised into the different languages of the consortium. The Translation Manager is a Web application with a front-end designed to allow users with different profiles (administrator, supervisor and translator) to manage translations of all relevant elements from English (the default language) into their own language.

1.1 Scope

This document describes the requirements of the Translation Manager software in terms of interface functionality and workflow. It also details the specification of APIs exposed by the Translation Manager software.

2. Definitions, acronyms e abbreviations

NAME	DESCRIPTION
KEY	Key element identifying a textual expression on emails, clinical documents, applications, eCREAM software
KMA	Key Manager Application - manages the key database
APPLICATION	Applications that use the Key
VALUES	Value that the key can take on
TASKS	Import procedure for entering keys
TM	Translation Manager
TMA	Translation Manager Application - for the localization of the eCREAM SW.
TM API	Translation Manager API – to provide and update translations in the different target languages of eCREAM applications

2.1 Modules catalogue

Figure 1– Architecture diagram

The TM software will consist of three modules:

- **KeyManager Application (KMA):** this module is used during the development phase of the eCREAM software by the Key Manager (KM). The KM manages the keys requested by the developer as textual elements used by the software. Keys are entered by identified with a unique code.

- **Translator Manager Application (TMA):** this module manages the localization of the eCREAM software, once development is complete. The TMA builds the workflow involving the translator and supervisor to validate the translation of keys for each language.
- **Translator Manager API (API):** this module handles the A2A interfaces between the Translation Manager tool and the eCREAM software. It provides and updates the translations entered by the KMA and validated by the TMA in the target languages for the eCREAM applications.

Figure 2 – Workflow sequence of the different modules

3. API

Translation Manager communicates via APIs allowing other external applications to interact with it.

APIs allow external applications that use the translation service to contact the Translation Manager in the role of translation service provider to receive the requested data.

The APIs exposed by Translation Manager are public and access is through HTTPS calls. No authentication process is implemented.

An example of a login is shown below:

1 – Login : Metodo POST

Request – `http://URL_TRANSLATION_MANAGER/api/login`

```
{  
  "username": "USER",  
  "password": "PASSWORD"  
}
```

Response

```
{"password":null,"username":"USER","authorities":[{"authority":"ADMIN"}],"accountNonExpired":true,"  
accountNonLocked":true,"credentialsNonExpired":true,"enabled":true,"tokenRequired":false,"otp":false  
,"userInfo":{"userId":1,"name":"Riccardo","surname":"Rossi"},"userId":1}
```

Below are the exposed APIs with examples of calls.

3.1 List of keys associated with the individual application

- `/bundle/{languageCode}/{applicationCode}` -> List of elements of type BundleModel
 - languageCode: Language code
 - applicationCode: System Application Code
 - Returns the list of all keys associated with a single application with the translations indicated by the parametron language

EXAMPLE

2 - /bundle/{languageCode}/{applicationCode} : Metodo GET

Request - `http://URL_TRANSLATION_MANAGER/api/bundle/IT/EDEHR`

```
{  
  "username": "USER",  
  "password": "PASSWORD"  
}
```

Response

```
[  
  {  
    "key": "12345",  
    "eCreamKey": "ec.ehr.dementia",  
    "definition": "Disease .....",  
    "values": [  
      {  
        "fullText": "Cogntive disorder",  
        "shortText": "Dementia",  
        "startDate": "30/01/2024",  
        "endDate": null,  
        "fullTextMaxLength": 30,  
        "shortTextMaxLength": 10  
      },  
      {  
        "fullText": "Dementia cognitive impairment",  
        "shortText": "Dementia",  
        "startDate": null,  
        "endDate": "30/01/2024",  
        "fullTextMaxLength": 30,  
        "shortTextMaxLength": 10  
      }  
    ]  
  },  
  {  
    ...  
  }  
]
```

3.2 List of keys associated with the individual application module

- /bundle/{languageCode}/{applicationCode}/{moduleCode} -> List of elements of type BundleModel
 - languageCode: Language code
 - applicationCode: System application code
 - moduleCode: Module application code
 - Returns the list of all keys associated with a single application module with the translations indicated by the parametron language.

EXAMPLE

3 - `/bundle/{languageCode}/{applicationCode}/{moduleCode}` : Metodo GET

Request - `http://URL_TRANSLATION_MANAGER/api/bundle/IT/DB/DBHO`

```
{
  "username": "USER",
  "password": "PASSWORD"
}
```

3.3 List of keys associated with the individual application element

- `/bundle/code/{languageCode}/{applicationCode}/{customCode}` -> single element BundleModel
 - languageCode: Language code
 - applicationCode: System Application Code
 - customCode: Key application code
 - Returns the translations indicated by the language parameter associated with a single application element.

EXAMPLE

4 - `/bundle/code/{languageCode}/{applicationCode}/{customCode}` : Metodo GET

Request - `http://URL_TRANSLATION_MANAGER/api/bundle/code/IT/DB/Test`

```
{
  "username": "USER",
  "password": "PASSWORD"
}
```

Response

```
{
  "key": "test",
  "eCreamKey": "TESTMAX002",
  "definition": "Test",
  "values": [
    {
      "fullText": "TestMaxcase002",
      "shortText": "c005",
      "startDate": null,
      "endDate": null,
      "fullTextMaxLength": 10,
      "shortTextMaxLength": 5
    }
  ]
}
```

3.4 Bundle model

- key: String
- eCreamKey: String
- definition: String
- values: List of BundleValueModel (1..n)
 - fullTex: String

- shortText: String
- startDate: Date;
- endDate: Date;
- fullTextMaxLength: Integer;
- shortTextMaxLength: Integer;

Date format: dd/MM/yyyy

4. ACTORS' MODEL

This chapter will explain the model and specification of actors using the service and the relationships between them. The model is described in Sections **4.1 Catalog of the actors** and **4.2 Hierarchy among Actors**.

4.1 Catalogue of the actors

The actor catalogue lists the names of the roles that identify the actors and their responsibilities to the service. Subcategories, i.e., specialisations of the actor, synonyms, and examples of actor instances, may be listed for each role.

The TM application provides management of the system roles enabled to use the Web Service.

The following table shows the list of expected roles with their definitions:

Name	Description / Responsibilities
Admin (current KEY MANAGER)	Manages the overall system, including user permissions and system configurations. The KM performs the task of providing SW developers with the correct key for each text used by the software. It uses the interface as a common vocabulary for the different applications of eCREAM.
Translator (Translator e Supervisor)	After the key is created, the creation notification is received, and the system takes care of the translation to the target language of the language for which it is configured and of eCREAM applications. The translator/supervisor must verify the translation in the target languages to the eCREAM applications.
User	Utilises the eCREAM software with the localised interface.

4.2 Hierarchy among actors

This section shows the diagram representing the actors involved in the use cases.

Figure 3- Actors involved in TM

4.3 Main flow

The main workflow involving the Key Manager (KM) begins when an eCREAM software developer requests a key for a text element needed in the software (SW). Here's how the process unfolds:

1. Key Request: The developer requests a key from the KM for a specific text element required in the eCREAM software.
2. Key Database Check: The KM searches the Key Database to check if there is an existing key that matches the request.
 - If an existing key is found that matches the request, the KM provides this key to the developer.
 - If no existing key matches the request, the KM creates a new key in the database.
3. Notification to Translators: After the key is created or provided, the Key Manager Application (KMA) notifies the translators about the new or updated key.
4. Key Provision to API: The KMA provides the newly created or updated key to the Translator Manager API (API). This API allows the eCREAM software to receive the bundle with the default version of the key (in English).

Translator Manager Application (TMA): This module manages the localization of the eCREAM software once the development phase is completed. TMA facilitates the workflow involving translators and translation supervisors for each target language.

Translator Manager API (API): This module is responsible for the Application-to-Application (A2A) interfaces between the Translation Manager tool and the eCREAM software. Its primary function is to provide and update translations in target languages for eCREAM applications.

Figure 4 - Use Case diagram

Figure 5- Key management workflow

5. CATALOGUE OF USE CASES

This section describes the implemented Use Cases.

5.1 Use case Access to TM

This use case addresses the functional requirement "Access to TM," through credentials.

It outlines how authorised operators can access the application and utilise its functionalities.

5.1.1 Access to TM

This section displays the diagram of the use case "Access to the TM" application with the relevant roles involved.

Figure 6 - Use case Access to TM

5.1.2 Access to TM – Scope

The use case describes TM operator access to the Translation Manager software.

5.1.3 Access to TM – Security and confidentiality requirements

Access to the use case in question is granted to the authorised operator with the role of:

- Admin (current KEY MANAGER)
- Translator (Translator/Supervisor)

5.1.4 Access to TM – Main flow

The main flow for accessing the TM platform is described below:

1. The authorised operator requests access to the TM application using credentials, assigned either as Admin or Translator roles. The KM accessing the platform does not receive any input bundles.
2. The system verifies the operator's authentication context data to determine login eligibility.
3. Upon successful verification, the operator logs in to the TM software.

5.1.5 Access to TM – Information covered

To log in to the platform with credentials, you must have the following input information:

- **Username**
- **Password**

In **bold**: mandatory information

Output information:

Access to TM

5.1.6 Access to TM – User interface

The system provides the operator accessing the platform with the Home and function menu.

The interface for user access is structured as follows:

- The first field requires mandatory input of the operator's username.
- The second field requires mandatory input of the operator's password. An option to toggle the password visibility is available by clicking the eye icon on the right.
- A "Login" button allows access to the platform's Home upon clicking.

The screenshot shows a login form titled "Translation Manager". It contains two input fields: "Username*" and "Password*". The "Password*" field has an eye icon on the right side, indicating a toggle for password visibility. Below the fields is a teal button with a right-pointing arrow and the text "LOGIN".

Figure 7 – Interface use case Access to TM

5.2 Use case Home view

This use case implements the functional requirement for "Home," which serves as the starting point for navigating the TM platform. It describes the functionality and features available on the HOME page of the Translation Manager.

5.2.1 Home TM – Roles

This section displays the diagram of the Home use case with its roles.

Figure 8– Use case Home TM

5.2.2 Home TM – Scope

This use case details the navigation within the TM platform starting from the HOME page, accessible upon logging into the platform with valid credentials. The primary objective of this phase of development is to establish the functional components and layout of the TM software's HOME page.

5.2.3 Home TM – Security and confidentiality requirements

Access to the use case in question is granted to the operator with the role of:

- Admin (current Key Manager)
- Translator

The operator accesses the platform using credentials and can view the TM Home and navigate within.

5.2.4 Home TM – Main flow

The main flow for displaying the TM Home will be described below:

1. The operator authenticates in the TM system through the credentials provided
2. The system opens the TM interface and displays the Home

3. The operator can navigate within the TM interface through the specific function-keys, according to his role.

5.2.5 Home TM – Information covered

To display the TM System Home, the following controls are required as input:

- Software access using credentials with Admin/Translator user

Output information:

Viewing the TM Home

5.2.6 Home TM – User Interface

The system makes the Home of the TM platform available. Depending on the login role, the operator displays the Home differently.

In the case of an operator logging in with the Admin role (current KEY MANAGER), the Home is displayed as follows:

- At the top left, the eCREAM logo functions as a key that allows you to return to the Home screen when navigating within the platform.
- Next, the top-level menu includes:
 - the "Add key" function key
 - the "Manage keys" function key
 - the "Translate" function key
- At the top right, a label displays the admin's first and last name, along with a key for accessing a second-level menu.
- At the top center, the image of the eCREAM project is displayed.
- In the center, the Translation Manager table with:
 - the first column "Application," representing the list of applications managed in eCREAM.
 - the Keys column, which shows the number of associated eCREAM keys for each application.
 - the Values column, which displays the different values that each key can take on in the different applications
 - the columns with the translations for all the languages used in the e-cream applications.

For each individual language, the percentage of confirmed translations is represented with two colors:

- Red indicates the percentage of translations that are incomplete.
- Green indicates the percentage of translations that are complete.

The percentage calculation for the values can be expressed using the proportion you provided:

$$\frac{\text{Values not validated}}{\text{Values}} = \frac{x}{100}$$

To find x:

$$x = \left(\frac{\text{Values not validated}}{\text{Values}} \right) \times 100$$

This formula will give you the percentage of values that have not been validated, based on the total number of values displayed in the dashboard.

Application	Keys(#)	Values(#)	Italian	Slovenian	Slovak	Polish	Greek
ED EHR	21	26	34% ↓	7% ↓	3% ↓	3% ↓	3% ↓
Dashboard	11	14	35% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓
Citizens mobile app	4	4	100% ↓	25% ↓	25% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓
Statistical analysis platform	3	4	25% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓
Citizens backend Service	25	27	85% ↓	29% ↓	3% ↓	0% ↓	3% ↓

Figure 9 – Interface use case Home TM – Admin

Next to the percentage, for each language and each application, there is a download symbol so that the Json can be downloaded, in which the variables and different values assigned to the key are described.

Adding a new key automatically generates the Json file, which can then be downloaded as described above. The downloaded Json is structured as follows:

- Key: represents the compiled key field and must be of type string.
- eCreamKey: displays the eCREAM code associated with the key and must be of type string.
- Definition: shows the description entered in the "definition" field and must be of type string.
- Values: indicates the values assigned to the key, categorised as:
 - fullText: string
 - shortText: string
 - startDate: date in the format dd/mm/yyyy
 - endDate: date in the format dd/mm/yyyy
 - fullTextMaxLength: integer
 - shortTextMaxLength: integer

with the fields filled in as in the example below:

```
[
  {
    "key": "action.save",
    "eCreamKey": "ec.action.save",
    "definition": "",
    "values": [
      {
        "fullText": "Salva",
        "shortText": null,
        "startDate": null,
        "endDate": null,
        "fullTextMaxLength": null,
        "shortTextMaxLength": null
      }
    ]
  }
],
```

Figure 10 – Json Interface

When an operator logs in with the role of Translator, the Home screen is displayed as follows:

- Top Left:
 - o the eCREAM logo, which functions as a button to return to the Home screen when navigating within the platform.
- Top-level menu:
 - o the "Translate" function key.
- Top right:
 - o the label displaying the operator's first and last name with a function key for a second-level menu.
- Top center:
 - o the eCREAM project image.
- Center, the Translation Manager table, which includes:
 - Application column: Lists the applications managed in TM.
 - Keys column: displays the number of eCREAM keys associated with each application.
 - Values column: Shows the different values that each key can take in the different applications.
 - Language columns: Displays only the languages assigned to the Translator. Each language column shows the percentage of confirmed translations, indicated by two colours:
 1. Red, when the percentage of translations is not complete
 2. Green, when the percentage of translations is complete

Next to the percentage, for each language and for each application, there is a download symbol. Clicking this allows the user to download the JSON file, which describes the variables and the different values assigned to the key.

Figure 11 – Interface use case Home TM – Translator SL - SK

Figure 12 – Interface use case Home TM – Translator IT

5.3 Use case Menu TM view

This use case implements the functional requirement "TM Menu" that can be displayed after logging in to TM via credentials and is used to be able to navigate within the TM platform.

5.3.1 Menu TM - Roles

This section shows the Menu TM use case diagram with the relevant roles involved.

Figure 13 – Use case Menu TM

5.3.2 Menu TM – Scope

This use case outlines the navigation within the TM platform by operators, allowing access to various menu items. The objective at this stage of development is to establish the functional "Menu" page, aligned with the operational flow of TM.

5.3.3 Menu TM – Security and confidentiality requirements

Access to the use case in question is granted to the licensed operator through access to the TM platform with credentials.

5.3.4 Menu TM – Main flow

The main flow for displaying the TM menu will be described below:

1. The operator authenticates in the TM system through the credentials provided as Admin or as Translator
2. The system opens the TM interface, according to the authenticated role, and the menu is displayed
3. The operator accesses the different menu items, based on the Admin or Translator role he/she authenticated with, and can click on the function-keys according to his/her navigation needs.

The operator, whether authenticated as Admin or Translator, can access an additional menu located on the right side next to their first and last name. By clicking on a function key represented by three dots, they can view software information such as the current version and last update. The "Logout" function key allows them to exit the software.

5.3.5 Menu TM – Information covered

To view the TM Menu, the following input checks must be performed:

- Login to the software using credentials with the Admin/Translator role
- Menu function-keys

Output information:

TM Menu Display

5.3.6 Menu TM – User interface

The system makes the function menu available; if the operator logs in as an Admin user, the following first-level menu is displayed:

- the Add key function key, by which a second-level menu is opened
 - Insert Key, by which a new page is opened
 - Import, from file by which you open a new page
 - Tasks, by which a new page is opened
- the "Manage keys" function key, by which you open a new page
- the "Translate" function key, by which a new page is opened

Figure 14 – Interface use case Menu of first level TM – Admin

Figure 15 – Interface use case Menu of second level TM - Admin

If the operator logs in as a Translator user, the following top-level menu is displayed:

- the "Translate" function key, through which a new page opens.

Figure 16 – Interface use case Menu of first level TM – Translator

In the case of the menu on the right, next to the user's name, the operator authenticating as Admin/Translator can perform the following actions via a function-key indicated by three dots:

- view software information (current version, last update) via the "About TM" function-key"
- Exit the software using the "Logout" function key"

Figure 17 - Interface menu - Admin

Figure 18 - Interface menu - Translator

Figure 19 - Interface menu

Figure 20 - Interface About TM

Once the box with information about the TM software is open, as in the figure above, the operator can close the window using the "Close" button-function.

5.4 Use case “Add Key” management

This use case implements the "Add key" functional requirement, through which a new key can be added into the TM platform. The section describes the use case related to the description of the "Add key" functionality of the Translation Manager.

5.4.1 Use case “Add key” roles management

This section shows the Add key use case diagram with the relevant roles involved.

Figure 21 – Use case Add key roles management

5.4.2 Add key – Scope

The use case describes how to enter a new key within the TM platform through the "Add key" functional page that can be reached from the HOME page, access to which is allowed through credentials.

From the Home page, in the upper left corner, the user with the application role ADMIN has two modes of creating new keys:

- Single key entry.
- Mass insertion through Excel files.

In addition, from this same menu it is possible to monitor insertion tasks.

5.4.3 Add key – Security and confidentiality requirements

Access to the use case in question is granted to the Admin user, with credential access to the TM Home page and the Add key functional page.

The admin user accessing the Add key functional page can enter new keys.

5.4.4 Add key – Main flow

The main flow for reaching the "Add Key" functional page is described below:

1. The operator authenticates in the TM system through the provided credentials, as Admin;
2. The system opens the TM interface, according to the authenticated role, and the menu is displayed;
3. The operator accesses the "Add key" menu item;
4. The SW developer who needs a key for a text element expresses his need to the Key Manager (Admin), who searches the Key DB (see KMA Use Case - Key Database Search) to see if a key corresponding to the request already exists;
5. If it exists, the KM notifies SW of its existence. If it does not exist, the KM adds it through the KMA.
6. The KM selects the "Add Key" functionality (Add new key).
7. The operator can choose to select in the second level menu the function keys:
 - Import key
 - Import from file
 - Tasks

5.4.5 Add key – Information covered

To use the TM "Add key" feature, the following input checks must be performed:

- Log in to the software using credentials with the Admin role
- Access the Add key functional page
- The information that the KM must fill in to add a new key:

Field name	Description	Format	Mandatory	Other controls
Code	It is the identifier of the key. The value should be self-explanatory. For example, the key identifier "waiting time" could be "waiting time".	Text	Yes	Unique identifier, no two keys have the same Code value.
Type of domain	Explains whether the key belongs to the health care domain or the SW element domain.	Text	Yes	Can take the values: - Healthcare - SW element
Type of health domain (Healthcare)	If Domain type = Healthcare, explain whether the text is customised within the eCREAM project, or whether it is standard, widely used terminology.	Text	Yes if Domain type = Healthcare	It can take the values: - Standard - Custom

Tag	List of words associated with the key, used to categorise and identify the key with the search function.	Text	No	
Module	List of eCREAM SWs that use this key.	Text	No	One of the forms recorded in the DB
Start of validity period	<p>For each key, there can exist a list of validity periods. For each period, there is a set of data whose value is valid only within the start date and end date.</p> <p>These key attributes are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Short test max char - Long test - Short test - Meaning. <p>This field represents the validity date of the attributes.</p>	Data	Yes	It cannot precede the end date of another validity period.
End of validity period	<p>This is the date when the attributes are no longer valid.</p> <p>If null, the current period has no defined end.</p>	Data	Yes only if there is a period whose start date is later than the start date of this period	It cannot precede the start date of the validity period.
Long text max char	Maximum number of characters allowed in the long test value	Integer	Yes	
Short text max char	Maximum number of characters allowed in the short test value	Integer	Yes, if the short test has a value	
Long test	This is the text shown by the eCREAM software, in the long text version.	Text	Yes	Number of characters \leq Long text max char i.e. characters you want to show on SW interface
Short test	It is the text shown by the eCREAM software, in the short version. The	Text	No	Number of characters \leq Short

	SW can show the short test when there is no space in the UI to show the long version.			text max char i.e. characters you want to show on SW interface
Meaning	Specific definition and explanation of the text entry associated with the key. May include the values of standard classifications/ontologies.	Text	Yes	

Output information:

- Access to the Add key functional page
- New key insertion
- The key is inserted and stored on the DB
- An "Operation completed" message is notified.

5.4.6 Add key – User Interface

The system makes available the ability to enter a new key within the TM system.

The interface is as follows:

- in the HOME the Admin user displays the top-level menu with the function key "Add key"

Figure 22 – Use case interface - Add key

5.5 Use case - Single Key Entry Management

This use case implements the "Add key" functional requirement, through which a new key can be added into the TM platform. The section describes the use case related to the insertion of the single key through the "Add key" functionality of the Translation Manager.

5.5.1 Single key entry - Roles

This section shows the diagram of the Single Key Entry use case with the relevant roles involved.

Figure 23 – Use case Single Key Entry Management

5.5.2 Single key entry – Scope

The use case describes how to enter a new key within the TM platform through the "Add key" functional page that can be reached from the HOME page, access to which is allowed through credentials.

From the Home page, in the upper left corner, the user with the application role ADMIN has two modes of creating new keys:

- Single key entry.
- Mass insertion through Excel file.

In this use case, a single key entry is described.

5.5.3 Single key entry – Security and confidentiality requirements

Access to the use case in question is granted to the Admin user, with credential access to the TM Home page and the Add key functional page.

The admin user accessing the Add key functional page can enter a new key through the "Import key" menu item.

5.5.4 Single key entry – Main flow

The main flow for entering a single key is described below:

1. The operator authenticates in the TM system through the provided credentials, as Admin;
2. The system opens the TM interface, according to the authenticated role, and the menu is displayed;
3. The operator accesses the "Add key" menu item;
4. The SW developer who needs a key for a text element expresses his or her need to the Key Manager (Admin), who searches the Key DB (see KMA Use Case - Searching the Key Database) to see if a key corresponding to the request already exists;
5. If it exists, the KM notifies SW of its existence. If it does not exist, the KM adds it through the KMA.
6. The KM selects the "Add Key" (Add New Key) feature, followed by "Insert Key".
7. The KM fills in all the necessary information to describe the key and confirms the values.
8. The KMA performs the validation checks.
9. If all checks are OK, the new key and all its attributes are stored in the Key DB and a confirmation message is shown to the user.
10. If any checks are KO, the new key is not stored and the KMA notifies the user of the errors. The process returns to step 6.

5.5.5 Single key entry – Information covered

To use the TM "Add key" feature with single key entry, the following input checks must be performed:

- Log in to the software using credentials with the Admin role
- Access the Add key functional page
- Access the "Import key" menu item.
- Process the input information described in section 5.4.5 Add key - Processed information

Output information:

- Access the Add key functional page
- New key insertion.
- The key is inserted and stored on the DB
- An "Operation completed" message is notified.

5.5.6 Single Key Entry – User Interface

In the specific case of inserting a single key, the user with Admin role (current KM) accesses the "Add Key" menu and by selecting the "Insert Key" item, the following interface appears:

+ Add key Manage keys Translate Riccardo Rossi

New Key

Key Information
Applications

Code*

Code is required

Domain*

Domain is required

Full Text

Max length
0

Text*

Long max length is required

Short Text

Max length
0

Text

Definition

Tags

Figure 24 – Use case Interface Add key – Insert key

The "Key information" tab shows all the fields that characterise each eCream key:

- Identifier [Code] eCream key (unique) - required
- Domain della chiave - required
- Full Text
 - Max length
 - Text – required
- Short Text
 - Max length
 - Text
- Description
- Tags

In the case where the domain is healthcare and the selected element type is standard, a possible association with Ontologies can be assigned. Up to "n" ontologies can be assigned.

New Key

Key information | Applications

Code* ec_gastro_salmonella | Domain* Healthcare | Element type* Standard

Ontology* | Code +1

Ontologies	Ontology code	Op.
ICD-9-CM	0030	

Full Text | Short Text

Max length | Text* GASTROENTERITE DA SALMONELLA

Definition | Definizione

Tags: salmonella gastroenterite Add new tag ...

Figure 25 - - Case Use Interface Add key – Insert key - Ontologies

It is possible to select the ontology type from several options via a drop-down menu, as follows:

Ontologies

Ontology | Code +1

ICD-10-CM | No ontologies selected

ICD-9-CM

LOINC

SNOMED CT

Text* | Short Text

Max length | 0

Text

Figure 26 – Use case Interface Add key – Insert key - Ontologies

The table below will specify the individual fields. All mandatory fields are marked in the UI in orange and with an *.

Applications

Figure 27 – Use case Interface Add key – Insert key – Mandatory fields

From 1 ...n applications can be linked to each key (Application Tab)

Each application is characterised by:

- Application-key
- Modules (optional)
- Custom Key - required

In more detail, the list of information that the KM has to fill in to add a new key can be found in Chapter 5.4.5 Add key - Information handled.

During the process of creating a new key, the system checks for similarity with existing keys in the eCREAM dictionary to ensure that no duplicate keys are generated.

If the key is already present the following notification message "Key code already exists!" is shown.

Figure 28 – Add key – existed key

5.6 Use Case Management Massive input through excel file

This use case implements the "Add key" functional requirement, allowing multiple keys to be inserted into the TM platform via bulk insertion using Excel files. It describes the process of adding new keys through the "Add key" functionality of the Translation Manager, specifically focusing on the bulk insertion method using Excel files.

5.6.1 Massive input through excel file – Roles

This section displays the diagram of the use case massive input through excel file with the relevant roles involved.

Figure 29 – Use case Massive input Management

5.6.2 Massive input via excel file – Scope

The use case outlines the process of inserting multiple keys into the TM platform using Excel files through the "Add key" functional page. Access to this functionality is granted via credentials from the HOME page.

From the Home page, top left, the user with the application role ADMIN has two modes of creating new keys:

- Single key entry.
- Massive insertion through Excel file.

In this use case, massive key entry is described.

5.6.3 Massive input via excel file - Security and confidentiality requirements

Access to this use case is granted to the Admin user, who can navigate to the Add key functional page from the TM Home page. Within the Add key functional page, the Admin user can import new keys using the "Import from file" menu item.

5.6.4 Massive input via excel file - Main Flow

The main flow for entering a single key is described below:

1. The operator authenticates in the TM system through the provided credentials, as Admin;
2. The system opens the TM interface, according to the authenticated role, and the menu is displayed;
3. The operator accesses the "Add key" menu item;
4. The SW developer who needs a key for a text element expresses his need to the Key Manager (Admin), who searches the Key DB (see KMA Use Case - Key Database Search) to see if a key corresponding to the request already exists;
5. If it exists, the KM notifies SW of its existence. If it does not exist, the KM adds it through the KMA.
6. The KM selects the feature "Add Key" (Add new key) and then "Import from file".
7. The KM proceeds to the excel file import operations to insert the keys
8. The KMA performs the validation checks.
9. If all checks are OK, the new keys and all their attributes are stored in the key DB and a confirmation message is shown to the user.
10. If any checks are KO, the new key is not stored and the KMA notifies the user of the errors. The process returns to step 8.

5.6.5 Massive input via excel file - Information processed

To use the TM "Add key" feature with massive key entry, the following input checks must be performed:

- Log in to the software using credentials with the Admin role
- Access the Add key functional page
- Access the "Import from file" menu item
- Process the input information described in Section 4.4.5 Add key - Processed information

Output information:

- Access the Add key functional page
- Insert new key
- The key is inserted and stored on the DB
- An "Operation completed" message is notified.

5.6.6 Massive input via excel file - User interface

In the specific case of the massive insertion of new keys, the user with Admin role (current KM) accesses the "Add Key" menu and selecting "Insert from file" the following interface appears:

Application	Keys(#)	Values(#)	Italian	Slovenian	Slovak	Polish	Greek
ED EHR	21	26	34%	7%	3%	3%	3%
Dashboard	11	14	35%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Citizens mobile app	5	6	66%	16%	16%	0%	0%
Statistical analysis platform	3	4	25%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Citizens backend Service	25	27	85%	29%	3%	0%	3%

Figure 30 – Use case Interface - Add key – massive entry menu

The operator accesses the "Add Key" menu and by selecting "Import from file" the following interface appears:

Import keys from file Import

Before uploading the file, make sure to have the right template and to have filled it out correctly.

[Download template](#)

Select the application to be associated with the keys

Application

↑

Drag and drop file here

or

[Browse for file](#)

No file selected

Figure 31 – Use case Interface Add key – massive entry - Insert from file

This function allows for the bulk insertion of keys from a source file. Before proceeding, it's crucial to ensure that the correct template is available and properly filled out.

By selecting the "Download template" function key, you can download the template in "Microsoft Excel 97-2003 Worksheet (.xls)" format to ensure accurate data entry.

Import keys from file

Before uploading the file, make sure to have the right template and to have filled it out correctly.

[Download template](#)

Figure 32 – Use case interface Add key – massive entry - Download template

After downloading, select Open file, as shown below, to open the file:

Figure 33 – Use case interface Add key – Massive input, Insert from file – Open file

Figure 34 – Use case Interface Add key – massive input – download file

The Excel file “keys_template.xls” that is downloaded must be filled in by the user with the following information:

- **KEY CODE:** the unique identifier of the key.
- **CUSTOM_CODE:** Application key selected from eCREAM keys.
- **DOMAIN:** Specifies whether the key belongs to the healthcare domain or the software element domain. The value and domain description are entered in the "keys_template.xls" in the dedicated "INSTRUCTION" compilation instruction sheet.
- **ELEMENT TYPE:** indicates if the element is Custom or Standard. The value and description of the element type are entered in the "keys_template.xls" in the dedicated "INSTRUCTION" compilation instruction sheet.
- **FULL TEXT:** text displayed by the eCREAM software, in the long version.
- **FULL TEXT MAX LENGTH:** Maximum characters allowed for the full text.
- **SHORT TEXT:** text shown by the eCREAM software, in the short version.
- **SHORT TEXT MAX LENGTH:** Maximum characters allowed for the short text.
- **DEFINITION:** Definition of the key.
- **TAGS:** Keywords associated with the key for categorization and search.
- **MODULES:** Modules associated with the key, depending on the chosen application.

- **ONTOLOGY** and **ONTOLOGY CODE**: Allows association with up to 5 ontologies. ONTOLOGY (n) represents the ontology name, ONTOLOGY CODE (n) represents its code. The value and description of the Ontology and Code are entered in the "keys_template.xls" in the sheet dedicated to the compilation "INSTRUCTION".

There are some instructions in the excel sheet downloaded with the template in the second sheet, which we give below:

TEMPLATE USAGE INSTRUCTIONS	
Domain accepted values	
Domain description	Domain value
Healthcare	HC
Software	SW
Element type accepted values	
Element type description	Element type value
Custom	CS
Standard	STD
Ontology accepted values	
Ontology description	Ontology value
ICD-10-CM	ICD10CM
ICD-9-CM	ICD9CM
LOINC	LOINC
SNOMED CT	SNOMED CT
Modules syntax	
Enter module codes separated by comma	

Element type should be valorised if Domain is HC.

In more detail, refer to the table of input information, given in Add key - Processed information Add key - Processed information.

Once the Excel file is prepared, to upload it to the TM platform, the user must select the application from the dropdown menu, and the drag-and-drop the file into the dedicated upload area or select it from

computer resources:

Import keys from file

Before uploading the file, make sure to have the right template and to have filled it out correctly.

Download template

Select the application to be associated with the keys

Application

 Drag and drop file here

or

Browse for file

No file selected

Figure 35 – Use case interface Add key – Massive entry - File to upload

After selecting the application from the drop-down menu and selecting the data source file to be uploaded, the user must click on the "import" function key.

Figure 36 – Use case interface Add key – Massive entry - Import

The data in the Excel file is imported, and at the end of the import attempt, the result is presented as follows: through a progress mask where the import task's progress can be monitored.

Specifically, the following is displayed in the mask:

- **Processed elements:** number of elements corresponding to the rows of the excel file that have been processed
- **Successfully processed elements:** number of elements corresponding to the rows of the excel file that have been successfully processed.
- **Element to be verified:** number of elements corresponding to the rows of the excel file that are to be verified i.e. identified as "To check" in the excel file condition that may occur in the case of the presence of ontology or text of the duplicate key
- **Incorrect elements:** number of elements corresponding to the rows of the excel file that are found to be in ERROR status

Import keys from file

Insertion task completed

Processed elements : 1

Successfully processed elements : 0

Elements to be verified : 0

Incorrect elements: 1

Delete task

Before uploading the file, make sure to have the right template and to have filled it out correctly.

Download template

Figure 37 – Use case Interface Add key – Massive input - Entered task progress

After the errors have been corrected, the import procedure can be run again.

The results can be accessed by clicking the "Insertion task completed" function button to download the file.

Import keys from file

Insertion task completed

Processed elements : 4

Successfully processed elements : 0

Elements to be verified : 0

Incorrect elements: 0

Delete task

Before uploading the file, make sure to have the right template and to have filled it out correctly.

Download template

Select the application to be associated with the keys

Application
Dashboard

Figure 38 – Use case Interface Add key – Massive input - download file

After saving the downloaded file, you can open the 'task_result.xls' file to review import errors and make necessary corrections for successful data loading. This file includes additional columns compared to the import file, displaying outcomes such as:

STATUS	ERRORS	CHECKS
ERROR	Invalid domain: Healthcare, Invalid element type : laboratory text	

Specifically:

- **STATUS:** indicates the import status and may display “ERROR: ... CHECK”.
- **ERRORS:** lists errors detected during the import phase.
- **CHECKS:** indicates the number of elements corresponding to the rows of the Excel file that require verification.
- **FORCE INSERT:** allows data to be forcibly inserted via Excel file and sent to the server through a forced import. Enter “1” in the FORCE INSERT cell to force insertion. If there are no errors but only checks, the key is inserted by forcing its creation.

In the case of errors, retrieve the keys_template.xls file to make necessary corrections and resubmit the import. If all the corrections are error-free, after resubmission to the eCREAM platform following the Import operation, the task result displays the completion level. Specifically, the "Successfully processed elements" field will show the same number of elements as in the "Processed elements" field.

Figure 39 – Use case Interface Add key – Massive entry– Import keys from file

When downloading the "task_results.xls" file again, the columns indicating the import outcome will be populated with the following values:

STATUS	ERRORS	CHECKS
OK		

Using the "Delete task" button, the user can delete the file corresponding to the import attempt. From the import task page, the user can view the execution of tasks. If any tasks are running, the Admin user can stop them and then delete them.

5.7 Use case - Manage Tasks

This use case implements the "Add key" functional requirement, through which tasks entered in the TM platform can be consulted. The section describes the use case related to the management of tasks through the "Add key" functionality of the Translation Manager.

5.7.1 Tasks -Roles

This section shows the Tasks use case diagram with the relevant roles involved.

Figure 40 – Use case Manage Tasks

5.7.2 Tasks - Scope

The use case describes the ability to consult/download/delete tasks entered in the TM platform, using the functional page "Add key" reachable from the HOME page, access to which is allowed via credentials.

From the Home page, in the upper left corner, the user with the Admin application role can click the "Tasks" menu item."

5.7.3 Tasks – Requisiti di sicurezza e riservatezza

Access to the use case in question is granted to the Admin user, with access via credentials to the TM Home page and the Add key functional page.

The admin user accessing the Add key functional page can manage tasks via the "Tasks" functional page.

5.7.4 Tasks – Main flow

The "Tasks" menu item allows the user to monitor the progress of imports. The main flow to reach the "Tasks" function is described below:

1. The operator authenticates in the TM system through the provided credentials as an Admin.
2. The system opens the TM interface, and the menu is displayed.
3. The operator accesses the "Add key" menu item.

4. The KM selects the "Tasks" feature.
5. The operator can perform the desired operations on the "Tasks" page.

5.7.5 Tasks – Information covered

To use the TM "Tasks" feature, the following input checks must be performed:

- Log in to the software using credentials with the Admin role
- Access the Add key functional page
- Access the "Tasks" menu item.

Output information:

- Access the Tasks functional page
- Download Task
- Delete TaskTask

5.7.6 Tasks – User interface

The user with Admin role (KM) accesses the "Add Key" menu by displaying the following menu:

Figure 41 – Use case interface Add key – Tasks

By selecting the "Tasks" item, the Import tasks interface appears, displaying the following columns:

- Import date: the date on which the import attempt was made.
- Task ID: the identifier of the import task.
- Application: the name of the eCREAM application for which the import attempt was made.
- Total elements: the number of elements corresponding to the rows in the excel file that were imported or attempted to be imported.
- Added: the number of elements corresponding to the rows of the excel file that were successfully added.
- Existing: the number of elements in the task corresponding to the rows of the excel file that elements already existed.
- In errors: the number of elements corresponding to the rows of the excel file that encountered errors during the import phase.
- To check: the number of elements corresponding to the rows of the excel file that must undergo the check phase.

- **Actions:** these are the actions that can be performed, including "Download result" with the download symbol, and "Delete task" with the trash symbol.

[+ Add key](#)
 [Manage keys](#)
 [Translate](#)
Riccardo Rossi

Import Tasks [Refresh](#)

Import data	Task ID	Application	Total elements	Added	Existing	In errors	To check	Actions
12/02/2024	80	ED EHR	1	1	0	0	0	
12/02/2024	74	ED EHR	1	0	0	1	0	
05/02/2024	73	ED EHR	2	1	0	0	1	
05/02/2024	72	ED EHR	2	0	0	2	0	
30/01/2024	71	ED EHR	1	0	0	0	1	
30/01/2024	70	ED EHR	1	0	0	1	0	
30/01/2024	69	ED EHR	1	0	0	1	0	

Figure 42 – Use case interface Add key – Import Tasks

Specifically, by clicking on the 'Download result' button, you can download the 'task_result.xls' file and review the import results to understand any errors and make the necessary corrections for successful data loading. Conversely, by clicking on the 'Delete task' button, you can delete the file corresponding to the import attempt.

5.8 Use case Manage “Manage Keys”

This use case implements the functional requirement "Manage keys," through which it is possible to search and modify the attributes of a key entered in the TM.

5.8.1 Manage keys – Roles

This section shows the Manage keys use case diagram with the relevant roles involved.

Figure 43 – Use case manage Manage keys

5.8.2 Manage keys – Scope

This section shows the use case diagram. The use case describes how to manage (search and edit attributes) an existing key within the TM platform via the Manage keys functional page, which can be accessed from the Home page using credentials.

A user with the ADMIN application role can access the “Manage keys” menu item to perform the following operations:

- Verify the existence of a key already present as a result of an entry request to the Key Manager.
- Modify a key attribute.

5.8.3 Manage keys – Security and confidentiality requirements

Access to the use case in question is allowed to the operator who logs in with Admin user through credentials to the TM platform.

The admin accessing the platform can view in the TM Home the navigation menu and access the functional page "Manage keys" and can navigate within.

5.8.4 Manage keys – Main flow

The main flow to reach the "Manage keys" functional page is described below:

1. The operator authenticates in the TM system using the provided Admin credentials.

2. The system opens the TM interface, based on the authenticated role, and the menu is displayed.
3. The Admin operator accesses the "Manage keys" menu item.
4. The operator can proceed with the desired operations on the "Manage keys" page.

5.8.5 Manage key – Information covered

To use the TM "Manage keys" feature, the following input checks must be performed:

- Log in to the software using credentials with the Admin role
- Access the Manage keys menu item.

Output information:

- Access the Manage keys functional page
- Verify the existence of a key already present because of an input request to the Key Manager.
- Edit an attribute of a key.

5.8.6 Manage key – User Interface

The system makes available the ability to edit a key within the TM platform. In HOME, the admin user displays the top-level menu with the "Manage key" function key as described in section "4.8.4 Manage keys - Main flow"

Application	Keys(#)	Values(#)	Italian	Slovenian	Slovak	Polish	Greek
ED EHR	21	26	34% ↓	7% ↓	3% ↓	3% ↓	3% ↓
Dashboard	11	14	35% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓
Citizens mobile app	4	4	100% ↓	25% ↓	25% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓
Statistical analysis platform	3	4	25% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓
Citizens backend Service	25	27	85% ↓	29% ↓	3% ↓	0% ↓	3% ↓

Figure 44 – Use case manage Manage keys menu

Once you have accessed the "Manage keys" functional page, you can see:

+ Add key **Manage keys** Translate

Filter

Code	Full text	Short text	Applications	State	Op.
A1	test onthology	onthology		●	
A2	Add			●	
BT_NEW	New		ED EHR	●	
BT_SAVE	Save		ED EHR	●	
Calcium blood	blood calcium result	Ca	ED EHR	●	
ec.acceptance.header	Patient reception in the emergency department		Citizens backend Service, Dashboard	●	
ec.action.create	Create		Citizens backend Service	●	
ec.action.save	Save		Citizens mobile app, Citizens backend Service	●	
ec.apporto_calorico	Calorie intake/kg weight		Citizens backend Service, Citizens mobile app, Dashboard	●	
ec.brother_symptoms_10_lbl	Cardiac disorder		Citizens backend Service	●	

Figure 45 – Use case manage Manage keys interface

The user can view the list of available keys, organised into the following columns:

- Code: indicates the eCREAM code of the key.
- Full text: provides the full text description of the key.
- Short text: provides the short text description of the key.
- Applications: lists the eCREAM applications associated with the key.
- State: indicates the state of the key.
- Op.: shows the possible operations with two function keys:
 - The pencil icon allows editing the selected key.
 - The trash can icon allows deleting the key.

To facilitate the search for a key to be edited, the user can use the filtering function described below.

5.9 Use case manage “Searching”

This use case implements the "Searching" functional requirement, which is available on the "Manage keys" functional page, through which keys entered in the TM platform can be searched through the help of filters.

5.9.1 Searching – Roles

This section shows the Searching use case diagram with the relevant roles involved.

Figure 46 – Use case Manage keys - Searching

5.9.2 Searching – Scope

The use case describes how to search for an existing key within the TM platform using the Filter option present within the Manage keys functional page, which can be accessed via credentials from the Home main menu.

From the Home page at the top left, the user with the ADMIN application role can access the "Manage Keys" menu and can perform the following operation:

- Search for existing keys using filters

5.9.3 Searching – Security and confidentiality requirements

Access to the use case in question is allowed to the operator who logs in with Admin user through credentials to the TM platform.

The admin accessing the platform can view the navigation menu in the TM Home and access the functional page "Manage keys" and can search for keys within via the Filter option.

5.9.4 Searching – Main flow

Once the user accesses the “Manage keys” menu item, they can use the Filter option within the “Manage keys” functional page to search for existing keys. The main flow to reach the "Searching" functionality is described below:

- The operator authenticates in the TM system using the provided Admin credentials.
- The system opens the TM interface, and the menu is displayed.
- The Admin operator accesses the "Manage keys" menu item.
- The operator clicks on the Filter function key and can search for the desired key by filling in the specific filters.

5.9.5 Searching – Information covered

To use the TM "Searching" feature, the following input checks must be performed:

- Log in to the software using credentials with the Admin role
- Access the Manage keys menu item
- Click the "Filter" function key

Output information:

- Access the Manage keys function page
- Key search using filters

5.9.6 Searching – User interface

The system makes available the ability to search for an existing key within the TM platform, among the keys in the list on the Manage keys functional page. In HOME, the admin user displays the top-level menu with the "Manage keys" function key; after selecting the menu item. "Manage Keys," the search mask appears, which is activated by entering conditions in the "Filter" field.

Code	Full text	Short text	Applications	State	Op.
A1	test onthology	onthology		●	
A2	Add			●	
BT_NEW	New		ED EHR	●	
BT_SAVE	Save		ED EHR	●	
ec.acceptance.header	Patient reception in the emergency department		Citizens backend Service, Dashboard	●	
ec.action.create	Create		Citizens backend Service	●	
ec.action.save	Save		Citizens mobile app, Citizens backend Service	●	
ec.apporto_calorico	Calorie intake/kg weight		Citizens backend Service, Citizens mobile app, Dashboard	●	
ec.brother_symptoms_10_lbl	Cardiac disorder		Citizens backend Service	●	
ec.brother_symptoms_11_lbl	Gastrointestinal complaints		Citizens backend Service	●	

Figure 47 – Use case Searching interface

The Admin user accesses the key list page and sets the filter values according to their search needs, by entering one or more of the following values: code, application, module, domain, text, ontology, ontology code, and tags.

Figure 50 – use case manage Editing key

5.10.2 Editing key – Scope

After accessing the “Manage keys” menu item, the Admin user can search for and edit the entered keys. Using the “Edit key” button, the user can:

- Edit the general data associated with the key.
- Modify the key values concerning temporal validity.
- Manage applications associated with the key.
- Visualise translations.

At this stage of development, the purpose of the work is to describe the "Editing key" functionality, following the flow of operation of the TM.

5.10.3 Editing key – Security and confidentiality requirements

Access to the use case in question is granted to the Admin user, through access to the TM platform with credentials and the "Menage keys" functional page”.

5.10.4 Editing key – Main flow

Below are the steps the admin user must follow to reach the "edit key" function:

1. Authenticate in the TM system using the provided Admin credentials.
2. The system opens the TM interface according to the authenticated role, and the menu is displayed
3. Access the "Menage keys" menu through the "Menage keys" function key.
4. On the key list page, identify a key and select the "Edit" action
5. The “Edit key” form opens, displaying the current values of the key attributes stored in the database. The form is in "editable" mode.
6. Edit the necessary values and confirm the operation using the "Save" button.
7. The system performs validation checks.

8. If all checks pass successfully, the new key and its attributes are stored in the Key DB, and a confirmation message is displayed to the user.
9. If any checks fail, the new key is not stored, and the KMA notifies the user of errors.

5.10.5 Editing key – Information covered

To use the TM “Editing key” feature, the following input checks must be performed:

- Log in to the software using credentials with the Admin role
- Access the Manage keys functional page
- Have the following input information described below in the table:

Field name	Description	Format	Mandatory	Other controls
Domain type	Explains whether the key belongs to the health domain or the SW element domain	Text	Yes	Can take the values: - Healthcare - SW element
Healthcare domain type	If Domain Type= Healthcare explains whether the text is customised within the eCREAM project, or whether it is standard, widely used terminology	Text	Yes if Domain Type= Healthcare	It can take the values: - Standard - Custom
Tag	List of words associated with the key, used to classify and identify the key using the search function	Text	No	
Module	List of eCREAM SWs using this key	Text	No	One of the modules registered in DB and whose code is known
Validity period start	For each key there can be a list of validity periods. For each period there is a set of data whose value is valid only within the start date and end date. These key attributes are: - Long test max car - Short test max car - Long test	Data	No	It cannot precede the end date of another validity period. There can be no validity periods that overlap even partially.

	- Short test -Sense This field is the date since the attributes are valid.			
Validity period end	This is the date when the attributes are no longer valid. If null, the current period has no defined end.	Data	Yes, only if there is a period whose start date is after the beginning of that period.	It cannot precede the end date of another validity period.
Long text max char	Maximum number of characters allowed in the long test value	Integer	Yes	
Short text max char	Numero massimo di caratteri ammessi nel valore del testo Breve	Integer	Yes, if Short test has a value	
Long test	This is the text shown by the eCREAM software, in the long version	Text	Yes	Number of character <= Long text max char
Short test	It is the text shown by the eCREAM software, in the short version. The SW can show the short test when there is no space in the user interface to show the long version.	Text	No	Number of character <= Short text max char
Definition	Specific definition and explanation of the text element associated with the Key. May include the values of standard classifications/ontologies	Text	No	

- The value of the code cannot be changed or deleted
- A new validity period can be added, with all associated attributes

Output information:

- Ability to modify the key
- “Operation completed” message
- Key stored in DBDB

5.10.6 Editing key – User interface

The user can view the list of available keys, organised into the following columns:

- Code: indicates the eCREAM code of the key.
- Full text: provides the full text description of the key.
- Short text: provides the short text description of the key.
- Applications: lists the eCREAM applications associated with the key.
- State: indicates the state of the key.
- Op.: shows the possible operations with two function keys:
 - The pencil icon allows editing the selected key.
 - The trash can icon allows deleting the key.

Code	Full text	Short text	Applications	State	Op.
A1	test ontology	ontology		●	
A2	Add			●	
BT_NEW	New		ED EHR	●	
BT_SAVE	Save		ED EHR	●	
Calcium blood	blood calcium result	Ca	ED EHR	●	
ec.acceptance.header	Patient reception in the emergency department		Citizens backend Service, Dashboard	●	
ec.action.create	Create		Citizens backend Service	●	
ec.action.save	Save		Citizens mobile app, Citizens backend Service	●	
ec.apporto_calorico	Calorie intake/kg weight		Citizens backend Service, Citizens mobile app, Dashboard	●	
ec.brother_symptoms_10_lbl	Cardiac disorder		Citizens backend Service	●	

Figure 51 – use case interface Manage - Editing key

To facilitate the search for a key to be edited, filtering can be used, via the “Filter” option by setting the search keys and selecting the “Search” function key (for a complete description of key searching, see Chapter 5.9 Use Case Management “Searching”).

After clicking the “Edit” button (indicated by the pencil symbol) associated with a chosen key, a new window opens where you can edit the key. In the edit interface, it is possible to override the following fields in the upper section:

- **Domain field** indicates whether the key belongs to the health domain or the SW elements domain, selectable via drop-down menu.
- **Element type**, choose whether it is standard or custom terminology from a drop-down menu.
- **Definition**, provide a description of the key.
- **Tags**, used to categorise and identify the key with the search function.

Additional tags can be added in the specific tag field:

In the lower space, you can edit the following fields:

- **Last value:** setting the previous value as full text and short text.
- **Key Values:** setting the previous value with start and end validity date.
- **Applications:** setting the applications with which the key is associated
- **Translations:** checking the translations made.

After making the changes, you can save them using the "Save" button.

For the full description of the fields, consult Chapter 5.4 Use Case "Add Key" Management.

Figure 52 – use case interface Editing key

5.11 Use case manage Translate

This use case implements the “Translate” functional requirement, which is available in the TM platform through TM access with Admin/Translator roles.

5.11.1 Translate – Roles

This section shows the Translate use case diagram with the relevant roles involved.

Figure 53 – use case manage Translate

5.11.2 Translate – Scope

This use case outlines the process of translating a new key within the Translation Manager (TM) platform, accessible from the HOME page upon logging in with appropriate credentials.

From the HOME page, users with the ADMIN or Translator (TM application) role can navigate to the “Translate” section located at the top left of the interface.

+ Add key Manage keys Translate Riccardo Rossi

Application	Keys(†)	Values(†)	Italian	Slovenian	Slovak	Polish	Greek
ED EHR	24	29	34%	6%	3%	3%	3%
Dashboard	13	16	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Citizens mobile app	6	7	0%	14%	0%	0%	0%
Statistical analysis platform	4	5	20%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Citizens backend Service	28	31	83%	25%	3%	0%	3%

Figure 54 – use case Translate - menu

5.11.3 Translate – Security and confidentiality requirements

Access to the use case in question is allowed to the operator who logs in with an Admin/Translator user account using credentials to the TM platform.

The operator with the admin/translator role accessing the platform can view in the TM Home the navigation menu and access the “Translate” functional page.”

5.11.4 Translate – Main flow

The main flow to reach the "Translate" functionality is described below:

1. The operator authenticates in the TM system using the provided Admin/Translator credentials.
2. The system opens the TM interface based on the authenticated role, and the menu is displayed.
3. The Admin/Translator operator accesses the "Translate" menu item.

5.11.5 Translate – Information covered

To use the TM “Translate” feature, the following input checks must be performed:

- Log in to the software using credentials with the Admin/Translator role
- Access the Translate menu item.

Output Information:

- Access the Translate functional page
- Searching for Translations

5.11.6 Translate – user interface

The system makes available the ability to check the status of translations on all keys entered into the system or the ability to timely check the translation on a key.

5.12 Manage “Translate” – Admin/Translator

The user with Admin/Translator role who accesses the "Translate" menu, visualises the following interface:

Language	Keys	Values	Validated values	Not validated values	Not translated values
1					
59	0				
67	0				
1					
67	0				

Figure 55 – Use case Translate – ADMIN

In this interface, you can visualise the available languages in the platform and the number of keys and their values:

- in "Green", the number of translated and validated values,
- in "Yellow", the number of translated and not validated values,
- in "Red," the number of untranslated values.

Selecting one of the "Green," "Yellow," or "Red" icons takes you to the page containing the list of translated and validated values, translated and non-validated values, and untranslated values, respectively.

5.12.1 Manage "Translate" – Validated value

The Admin/Translator user who selects the "Green" icon enters the page containing the list of translated and validated values.

Key Code	Start date	End date	Definition	Full text	Translated full text	Short text	Translated short text	Op.
A2				Add	Aggiungi			
BT_NEW			New button	New	Nuovo			
BT_SAVE			Save button	Save	Salva			
ec.acceptance.header			Text placed in the main section of the acceptance form	Patient reception in the emergency department	Accoglienza dei pazienti nel reparto di emergenza			
ec.action.create				Create	Creare			
ec.action.save				Save	Salva			
ec.apporto_calorico				Calorie intake/kg weight	Apporto calorico/kg di peso			
ec.brother_symptoms_11_lbl				Gastrointestinal complaints	Disturbi gastrointestinali			
ec.brother_symptoms_12_lbl				Liver disorders	Disturbi del fegato			

Figure 56 – Use case Translate - Validate value

The translation language and "validation" status of keys and key values are displayed in the upper left.

From this interface it is possible to visualise the list of values that have been translated and validated, or to use the Filter option to search for a specific key.

Key Code	Start date	End date	Definition	Full text	Translated full text	Short text	Translated short text	Op.
A2				Add	Aggiungi			
BT_NEW			New button	New	Nuovo			
BT_SAVE			Save button	Save	Salva			
ec.acceptance.header			Text placed in the main section of the acceptance form	Patient reception in the emergency department	Accoglienza dei pazienti nel reparto di emergenza			
ec.action.create				Create	Creare			
ec.action.save				Save	Salva			
ec.apporto_calorico				Calorie intake/kg weight	Apporto calorico/kg di peso			
ec.brother_symptoms_11_lbl				Gastrointestinal complaints	Disturbi gastrointestinali			
ec.brother_symptoms_12_lbl				Liver disorders	Disturbi del fegato			

Figure 57 – use case Translate - Filter

Selecting "Filter" opens the detailed search mask where you can set the various criteria.

Figure 58 – Use case Translate – filter mask

After setting the search criteria, select the "Search" button to perform the search.

To clear the fields and set a new search, select "Reset".

The search results will display all the keys that meet the set criteria. For each key, the following details are visualised:

- Key Code: the unique identifier of the key.
- Start date: the validity start date of the key value
- End date: the end validity date of the key value
- Definition: describes the meaning of the key value
- Full text: the text shown by the eCREAM software in the long text version
- Translated full text: the translated text shown by the eCREAM software in the long text version
- Short text: the text shown by the eCREAM software in the short text version
- Translated short text: the translated text shown by the eCREAM software in the short text version
- Op: is the column that identifies the operations that can be performed, indicated by the appropriate symbol

Key Code	Start date	End date	Definition	Full text	Translated full text	Short text	Translated short text	Op
A2				ADD	ADD/AGGI			+
EPUB01			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB02			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB03			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB04			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB05			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB06			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB07			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB08			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB09			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB10			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB11			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB12			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB13			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB14			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB15			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB16			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB17			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB18			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB19			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB20			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB21			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB22			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB23			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB24			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB25			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB26			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB27			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB28			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB29			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB30			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB31			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB32			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB33			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB34			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB35			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB36			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB37			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB38			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB39			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB40			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB41			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB42			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB43			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB44			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB45			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB46			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB47			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB48			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB49			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB50			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB51			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB52			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB53			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB54			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB55			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB56			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB57			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB58			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB59			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB60			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB61			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB62			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB63			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB64			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB65			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB66			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB67			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB68			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB69			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB70			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB71			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB72			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB73			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB74			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB75			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB76			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB77			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB78			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB79			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB80			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB81			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB82			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB83			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB84			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB85			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB86			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB87			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB88			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB89			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB90			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB91			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB92			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB93			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB94			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB95			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB96			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB97			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB98			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB99			Non button	Non	Non			+
EPUB100			Non button	Non	Non			+

Figure 59 – use case Translate - searching filter

By selecting "edit translation," the following screen appears:

+ Add key Manage keys Translate Riccardo Rossi

Translate > Validated > A2

Key: **A2**

Domain
Software

Definition

Italian translation

<p>Full Text</p> <p>Max length</p> <p>Text Add</p> <p>Translated Text Agglungi</p>	<p>Short Text</p> <p>Max length</p> <p>Text</p> <p>Translated Text</p>
--	--

Figure 60 – use case Translate - edit translation

In the upper left corner, the language of the translation is displayed.

In the main area of the window, the key code is shown along with all the fields being edited.

5.12.2 Manage “Translate” – Not validated value

When the Admin/Translator user selects the "Yellow" icon, you enter the page displaying a list of translated but unvalidated values. The translation language and the "not validated" status of keys and key values are displayed in the upper left corner.

From this interface, it is possible to view the list of values that have been translated but not yet validated, or to search for a specific key.

Key Code	Start date	End date	Definition	Full text	Translated full text	Short text	Translated short text	Op
A1			test oncology	test oncology	test di oncologia	orthology	ortologia	
Calcium blood			Laboratory test	blood calcium result	risultato del calcio nel sangue	Ca	Ca	
ec.brother_symptoms_T1_24			Cardiac disorder	Cardiac disorder	Disturbo cardiaco			
ec.btm.vase			View single red item	View single red item	Visualizza un singolo articolo rosso			
ec.cancel.bst			Cancel operation	Cancel operation	Annullamento dell'operazione			
ec.drug			Label pagina dei trattamenti	Treatment	Tattamento			
ec.ahc.dementia	30/01/2024		Disease ...	Cognitive disorder	Disturbo cognitivo	Dementia	Demenza	
ec.ahc.dementia		30/01/2024	Disease ...	Dementia cognitive impairment	Demenza cognitiva	Dementia	Demenza	
ec.amoglobin		01/03/2024	Hemoglobin (haemoglobin)[E] Hb or Hgb) is a protein containing iron that facilitates the transport of oxygen in red blood cells. Almost all vertebrates contain hemoglobin. [E] with the exception of the fish family Channichthyidae[E] and the tissues of some invertebrate animals. Hemoglobin in the blood carries oxygen from the respiratory organs (lungs or gills) to the other tissues of the body, where it releases the oxygen to enable aerobic respiration which powers the animal's metabolism. A healthy human has 12 to 20 grams of hemoglobin in every 100 mL of blood. Hemoglobin is a metalloprotein, a chromoprotein, and dimeric.	Hemoglobin	Emoglobina	HbG	HbG	

Figure 61 – Use case Translate - list of translated and non-validated values

Selecting "Filter" opens the detailed search mask where you can set the various criteria.

Figure 62 – use case Translate - Filter (non-validated)

After setting the search criteria, you click the "Search" button to execute the search. To clear the fields and start a new search, you must click "Reset".

The search results display all keys that meet the specified criteria. For each key, the following information is shown:

- Key Code: the unique identifier of the key. The value should be self-explanatory.
- Start date: the start validity date of the key value.
- End date: the end validity date of the key value.
- Definition: describes the meaning of the key value.
- Full text: the text shown by the eCREAM software in the long text version.
- Translated full text: the translated text shown by the eCREAM software in its long text version.
- Short text: the text shown by the eCREAM software in its short text version.
- Translated short text: the translated text shown by the eCREAM software in its short text version.
- Op: this column identifies available operations. The pencil symbol represents editing of the translation ("edit translation"), while the checkmark symbol represents validation of the translation.

Figure 63 – Use case Translate - operations

By selecting “edit translation,” the following screen appears:

Translate > IT To be validated > Calcium blood

Key: Calcium blood

Domain
Software

Definition
Laboratory text

Validate

Italian translation

Full Text

Max length

Text
blood calcium result

Translated Text
risultato del calcio nel sangue

Short Text

Max length

Text
Ca

Translated Text
Ca

Figure 64 – Use case Translate - edit translation

In the upper left corner, the language of translation is displayed.

In the main area of the window, the key code is displayed along with associated all fields available for editing and validation.

After making the necessary changes, you can validate the changes by selecting the "Validate" button.

If you only need to validate a translation without making further edits, you can directly select the "Validate" button. The action will return you to the mask displaying the list of translated values that have not yet been validated.

5.12.3 Manage “Translate” – Not translated value

When the Admin/Translator user selects the "Red" icon, it is possible to access the page displaying a list of untranslated values.

Figure 65 - Manage case Translate – not translated values

In the upper left corner, the translation language and the status of keys labelled as "Not translated" are displayed.

From this interface, it is possible to view the list of values that require translation and validation. Additionally, you can use the Filter feature to search for a specific key that needs to be translated.

Figure 66 – Use case Translate - filter (not translated values)

Selecting "Filter" opens a detailed search mask where various criteria can be set.

After configuring the search criteria, click the "Search" button to execute the search.

To clear the fields and start a new search, click “Reset”.

The search results display all keys that meet the specified criteria, showing the following details for each key:

- Key Code: unique identifier of the key.
- Start date: start validity date of the key value.
- End date: end validity date of the key value.

- Definition: description of the key value’s meaning.
- Full text: text displayed in the eCREAM software in its long form.
- Translated full text: translated text displayed in the eCREAM software in its long form.
- Short text: text displayed in the eCREAM software, in its short form.
- Translated short text: translated text displayed in the eCREAM software in its short form.
- Op: column indicating available operations; the pencil symbol allows editing of the translation ("edit translation"), while the check mark symbol signifies validation of the translation ("Validate translation").

Figure 67 – use case Translate - operations

By selecting “edit translation,” the following screen appears:

Figure 68 – Use case Translate - edit translation

In the upper left corner, the language of the translation is displayed.

In the main area of the window, the key code is shown along with all the fields being edited. 70

After making the necessary changes, it is possible to validate the changes by selecting the “Validate” button.

Annex 2

TRANSLATION MANAGER

User Manual

Project: eCREAM

enabling Clinical Research in Emergency and Acute care Medicine through automated data extraction

Call: HORIZON-HLTH-2021-TOOL-06

Topic: HORIZON-HLTH-2021-TOOL-06-03

Type of action: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions

Grant Agreement no. 101057726

SUMMARY

1.	PURPOSE AND SCOPE	5
2.	Definitions, acronyms and abbreviations	5
3.	ENABLING UTILITIES.....	5
4.	ADMIN USER	5
4.1	TM PLATFORM ACCESS	5
4.2	PASSWORD CHANGE OR RECOVERY	7
4.3	HOME PLATFORM	7
4.4	MENU TABS	8
4.4.1	ADD KEY tabs.....	8
4.4.1.1	Insert key	10
4.4.1.2	Import from file	13
4.4.1.3	Tasks	18
4.2	MANAGE KEYS tabs	19
4.2.1	Searching.....	21
4.2.2	Editing key.....	22
4.3	TRANSLATE tab.....	24
4.3.1	Validated value.....	25
4.3.2	Not validated value	27
4.3.3	Not translated value.....	29
5.	TRANSLATOR USER	31
5.1	ACCESS TO TM PLATFORM.....	31
5.2	PASSWORD CHANGE OR RECOVERY	33
5.3	HOME PLATFORM	33
5.4	MENU TABS	34
5.4.1	TRANSLATE tab.....	34
5.4.2	Validated value.....	35
5.4.3	Not validated value	38
5.4.4	Not translated value.....	40

List of figure

Figure 1 - TM platform login – admin.....	6
Figure 2 - TM platform login – credentials	6
Figure 3- Home TM use case interface - Admin	7
Figure 4 - Json interface.....	8
Figure 5 - Menu	8
Figure 6 – second level Menu.....	9
Figure 7 - Insert key	9
Figure 8 - Import from file	10
Figure 9 - Import tasks.....	10
Figure 10 - Add key - Insert key	11
Figure 11 - Add key – Insert key	12
Figure 12 - Add key - Insert Key - Ontologies	12
Figure 13 - Add key - Insert Key.....	12
Figure 14 - Add key - Insert Key – Save the new key	13
Figure 15 - Add key – existing key	13
Figure 16 – Add key – Mass input - Insert from file	13
Figure 17 – Add key – Mass input - Download template	14
Figure 18 - Add key – Massive input, Insert from file – Open file	14
Figure 19 - Massive input interface	14
Figure 20 - Add key – Mass input - File to upload	15
Figure 21 –Add key – Mass input - Import	16
Figure 22 –Add key – Mass input - Progress input task.....	16
Figure 23 – Add key – Mass input – download file.....	17
Figure 24 – Add key – Mass input – Import keys from file.....	18
Figure 25 – Add key – Import Tasks.....	19
Figure 26 – Manage keys menu.....	20
Figure 27 –Manage keys interface	20
Figure 28 – Searching surface.....	21
Figure 29 – Searching Filter	21
Figure 30 – Searching function keys search and reset	22
Figure 31 – Searching	22
Figure 32 – editing key	23
Figure 33 – Tags.....	23
Figure 34 - Editing key	24
Figure 35 - Menu translate	24
Figure 36 - Translate.....	25
Figure 37 - Translate - Validated value.....	25
Figure 38 - Translate - Filter.....	26
Figure 39 - Translate - filter	26
Figure 40 - Translate - searching filter.....	27

Figure 41 - Translate - edit translation	27
Figure 42 - Translate - list of translated and non-validated values	28
Figure 43 - Translate - Filter (non-validated).....	28
Figure 44 - Translate - operations	29
Figure 45 - Translate - edit translation	29
Figure 46 - Translate - values not translated.....	29
Figure 47 - Translate - filter (values not translated).....	30
Figure 48 - Translate - operations	30
Figure 49 - Access to the TM platform - translator	32
Figure 50 - TM platform access - credentials	32
Figure 51 - Home TM – Translator SL - SK	33
Figure 52 - Json	34
Figure 53 - Menu translate	35
Figure 54 – Translate	35
Figure 55 - Translate - Valited value	36
Figure 56 - Translate - Filter.....	36
Figure 57 - Translate - filter	37
Figure 58 - Translate - searching filter.....	37
Figure 59 - Translate - edit translation	38
Figure 60 - Translate - list of translated and non-validated values	38
Figure 61 - Translate - Filter (not validated).....	39
Figure 62 - Translate - operations	39
Figure 63 - Translate - edit translation	40
Figure 64 - Translate – not translated values.....	40
Figure 65 - Translate - filter (not translated values).....	41
Figure 66 - Translate - operations	41
Figure 67 - Translate - edit translation	42

1. PURPOSE AND SCOPE

The Translation Manager is a web application with a front-end designed to allow users with different profiles (admin, translator) to manage translations of all elements in eCREAM applications from English (the default language) to their own language.

2. Definitions, acronyms and abbreviations

NAME	DESCRIPTION
KEY	Key element identifying a textual expression on emails, clinical documents, applications, eCREAM software
KMA	Key Manager Application – manages the key database
APPLICATION	Applications that use the Key
VALUES	Value that Key can take on
TASKS	Import procedure for entering keys
TM	Translation Manager
TMA	Translation Manager Application – for the localization of the eCREAM SW.
TM API	Translation Manager API – To provide and update translations in the different target languages of eCREAM applications

3. ENABLING UTILITIES

Only authorised users can access the Translation Manager application; Users who need access to the TM platform must request credentials from the support team and access the TM platform from the link translation.ecreamproject.eu

The TM application can be enabled to users who can assume two possible roles:

- **Admin:** User who manages the Key Database.
- **Translator:** The translator/supervisor must verify the translations in the target languages to the eCREAM applications.

Based on role, some platform features are enabled or disabled.

4. ADMIN USER

Admin: a user who manages the Key Database.

4.1 TM PLATFORM ACCESS

From the login link, you can see the following screen:

Translation Manager

Username*

Password*

→ LOGIN

Figure 1 - TM platform login – admin

To access the platform correctly, you must fill in all required fields: the Username and Password, provided by the support team, will serve as your login credentials for the TM platform.

Translation Manager

Username*
admin

Password*
.....

→ LOGIN

Figure 2 - TM platform login – credentials

After entering the Username and Password, click the Login button accesses the Platform.

4.2 PASSWORD CHANGE OR RECOVERY

To change the password, you need to contact the Support team.

4.3 HOME PLATFORM

With the Admin role, you can see:

- At the top left, the eCREAM logo functions as a key that allows you to return to the Home screen when navigating within the platform.
- Next, the top-level menu includes:
 - the "Add key" function key
 - the "Manage keys" function key
 - the "Translate" function key
- At the top right, a label displays the admin's first and last name, along with a key for accessing a second-level menu.
- At the top center, the image of the eCREAM project is displayed.
- In the center, the Translation Manager table with:
 - the first column "Application," representing the list of applications managed in eCREAM.
 - the Keys column, which shows the number of associated eCREAM keys for each application.
 - the Values column, which displays the different values that each key can take on in the different applications
 - the columns with the translations for all the languages used in the e-cream applications.

For each individual language, the percentage of confirmed translations is represented with two colors:

- Red indicates the percentage of translations that are incomplete.
- Green indicates the percentage of translations that are complete.

Application	Keys(#)	Values(#)	Italian	Slovenian	Slovak	Polish	Greek
ED EHR	21	26	34% ↓	7% ↓	3% ↓	3% ↓	3% ↓
Dashboard	11	14	35% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓
Citizens mobile app	4	4	100% ↓	25% ↓	25% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓
Statistical analysis platform	3	4	25% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓	0% ↓
Citizens backend Service	25	27	85% ↓	29% ↓	3% ↓	0% ↓	3% ↓

Figure 3- Home TM use case interface - Admin

Next to the percentage, for each language and each application, there is a download symbol. This allows you to download the Json file, which describes the variables and the different values assigned to each key.

The following is an example:

```
[
  {
    "key": "action.save",
    "eCreamKey": "ec.action.save",
    "definition": "",
    "values": [
      {
        "fullText": "Salva",
        "shortText": null,
        "startDate": null,
        "endDate": null,
        "fullTextMaxLength": null,
        "shortTextMaxLength": null
      }
    ]
  }
],
```

Figure 4 - Json interface

Adding a new key automatically generates the Json file, which can then be downloaded as described above. The downloaded Json is structured as follows:

- Key: represents the compiled key field and must be of type string.
- eCreamKey: displays the eCREAM code associated with the key and must be of type string.
- Definition: shows the description entered in the "definition" field and must be of type string.
- Values: indicates the values assigned to the key, categorised as:
 - fullText: string
 - shortText: string
 - startDate: date in the format dd/mm/yyyy
 - endDate: date in the format dd/mm/yyyy
 - fullTextMaxLength: integer
 - shortTextMaxLength: integer

4.4 MENU TABS

4.4.1 ADD KEY tabs

The “Add key” tab provides the functionality to insert a new key within the TM system. This feature is accessible for viewing and editing exclusively by users with the Admin role, through the “Add key” menu item.

Figure 5 - Menu

Through the “Add key” menu item, users can access a second-level menu and click on the following options:

Figure 6 – second level Menu

In particular, the Admin can access the following options in the second-level menu:

- **Insert Key.** Allows the insertion of a new single key by filling out the specific screen (* denotes required fields).

The screenshot shows the 'New Key' form. At the top, there are navigation links: '+ Add key', 'Manage keys', and 'Translate'. The user's name 'Riccardo Rossi' is in the top right. The form is divided into two main sections: 'Key information' and 'Applications'.
 Under 'Key information':
 - 'Code*' is 'ec.gastro_salmonella'.
 - 'Domain*' is 'Healthcare'.
 - 'Element type*' is 'Standard'.
 - 'Ontology*' is a dropdown menu.
 - 'Code' is a text field with a '+1' icon.
 - 'Ontologies' section contains a table with columns 'Ontology', 'Ontology code', and 'Op.'. One row shows 'ICD-9-CM' with code '0030' and a red 'X' in the 'Op.' column.
 - 'Full Text' section has a 'Max length' field and a 'Text*' field containing 'GASTROENTERITE DA SALMONELLA'.
 - 'Short Text' section has a 'Max length' field and a 'Text' field.
 - 'Definition' section is labeled 'Definizione ...'.
 - 'Tags' section shows 'salmonella' and 'gastroenterite' with an 'Add new tag ...' button.
 A green '+1' icon is visible in the bottom right corner of the form.

Figure 7 - Insert key

- **Import from file:** allows bulk insertion of keys from a source file:

Figure 8 - Import from file

- **Tasks:** allows consultation of tasks entered in the TM platform:

Import data	Task ID	Application	Total elements	Added	Existing	In errors	To check	Actions
12/02/2024	80	ED EHR	1	1	0	0	0	
12/02/2024	74	ED EHR	1	0	0	1	0	
05/02/2024	73	ED EHR	2	1	0	0	1	
05/02/2024	72	ED EHR	2	0	0	2	0	
30/01/2024	71	ED EHR	1	0	0	0	1	
30/01/2024	70	ED EHR	1	0	0	1	0	
30/01/2024	69	ED EHR	1	0	0	1	0	

Figure 9 - Import tasks

4.4.1.1 Insert key

The “Insert Key” menu item allows an Admin user to add a new key to the TM platform. After selecting the “Add key” menu item, followed by the “Insert Key” menu item, the Admin user can enter all necessary information needed to describe the key on the “Insert key” page and confirm the values.

- If all the checks pass successfully, the new key and its attributes are stored in the Key DB, and a confirmation message is displayed to the user.
- If any check fails, the new key is not stored, and the user is notified of errors by the KMA.

+ Add key Manage keys Translate Riccardo Rossi

New Key

Key Information
Applications

Code*

Code is required

Domain*

Domain is required

Full Text

Max length
0

Text*

Long max length is required

Short Text

Max length
0

Text

Definition

Tags

+

Figure 10 - Add key - Insert key

The "Key information" tab displays all fields that characterise each eCream key and the requiredness:

- Identifier [Code] key eCream (unique) - required
- Domain of the key - required
- Full Text
 - Maximum length
 - Text - required
- Short Text
 - Maximum length
 - Text
- Description
- Tags

If the domain is healthcare and the selected element type is standard, up to 4 ontologies can be associated, as shown below.

Figure 11 - Add key – Insert key

The ontology type can be selected from several options available in a drop-down menu, including:

Figure 12 - Add key - Insert Key - Ontologies

All mandatory fields are highlighted in orange in the UI and marked with an *.

To confirm the addition of the key, you must click the "+" button located in the lower right corner:

Figure 13 - Add key - Insert Key

To confirm the entry, you need to select the "Save" button that appears in the upper right corner after adding the key:

Figure 14 - Add key - Insert Key – Save the new key

From 1 ...n applications can be linked to each key (Application Tab). Each application is characterised by:

- Application-key
- Modules (optional) directly related to the application-key
- Custom Key (required)

During the creation of a new key, the system checks for similarity with keys already in the eCREAM dictionary. If a similar key already exists, a notification message "Key code already exists!" is displayed. This notification appears when a key with a similar definition is entered.

If no similarity key is found, the key is created normally. Otherwise, the following notification appears:

Figure 15 - Add key – existing key

4.4.1.2 Import from file

The "Import from file" menu item allows the addition of one or more new keys to the TM platform.

The steps for the Admin user are summarised below:

- The Admin selects the "Add Key" feature (Add new key) and then chooses "Import from file"
- The Admin proceeds with importing the keys from an Excel file
- The KMA performs validation checks
- If all checks pass successfully, the new keys and all their attributes are stored in the Key DB, and a confirmation message is shown to the user.
- If any checks fail, the new keys are not stored, and the KMA notifies the user of errors.

Users accessing the "Add Key" menu and selecting the "Import from file" will see the following interface:

Figure 16 – Add key – Mass input - Insert from file

Selecting the "Download template" function key downloads the template in "Microsoft Excel 97-2003 Worksheet (.xls)" format for correct data entry.

Import keys from file

Before uploading the file, make sure to have the right template and to have filled it out correctly.

Figure 17 – Add key – Mass input - Download template

After downloading, the user should select **Open file**, as shown below, to save the file:

Figure 18 - Add key – Massive input, Insert from file – Open file

Figure 19 - Massive input interface

The Excel file “keys_template.xls” that is downloaded must be filled in by the user with the following information:

- **KEY CODE:** the unique identifier of the key.
- **CUSTOM_CODE:** Application key selected from eCREAM keys.
- **DOMAIN:** Specifies whether the key belongs to the healthcare domain or the software element domain. The value and domain description are entered in the "keys_template.xls" in the dedicated "INSTRUCTION" compilation instruction sheet.
- **ELEMENT TYPE:** indicates if the element is Custom or Standard. The value and description of the element type are entered in the "keys_template.xls" in the dedicated "INSTRUCTION" compilation instruction sheet.
- **FULL TEXT:** text displayed by the eCREAM software, in the long version.
- **FULL TEXT MAX LENGTH:** Maximum characters allowed for the full text.
- **SHORT TEXT:** text shown by the eCREAM software, in the short version.
- **SHORT TEXT MAX LENGTH:** Maximum characters allowed for the short text.
- **DEFINITION:** Definition of the key.
- **TAGS:** Keywords associated with the key for categorization and search.
- **MODULES:** Modules associated with the key, depending on the chosen application.
- **ONTOLOGY** and **ONTOLOGY CODE:** Allows association with up to 5 ontologies. ONTOLOGY (n) represents the ontology name, ONTOLOGY CODE (n) represents its code. The value and description of the Ontology and Code are entered in the "keys_template.xls" in the sheet dedicated to the compilation "INSTRUCTION".

Once the Excel file is prepared, to upload it to the TM platform, the user must select the application from the dropdown menu, and the drag-and-drop the file into the dedicated upload area or select it from computer resources:

Import keys from file

Before uploading the file, make sure to have the right template and to have filled it out correctly.

Download template

Select the application to be associated with the keys

Application

Drag and drop file here

or

Browse for file

No file selected

Figure 20 - Add key – Mass input - File to upload

After selecting the application from the drop-down menu and selecting the data source file to be uploaded, the user must click on the "import" function key.

Figure 21 –Add key – Mass input - Import

The data in the Excel file is imported, and at the end of the import attempt, the result is presented as follows: through a progress mask where the import task's progress can be monitored.

Figure 22 –Add key – Mass input - Progress input task

The results can be accessed by clicking the "Insertion task completed" function button to download the file.

Figure 23 – Add key – Mass input – download file

After saving the downloaded file, you can open the 'task_result.xls' file to review import errors and make necessary corrections for successful data loading. This file includes additional columns compared to the import file, displaying outcomes such as:

STATUS	ERRORS	CHECKS
ERROR	Invalid domain: Healthcare, Invalid element type: laboratory text	

Specifically:

- **STATUS**: indicates the import status and may display “ERROR: ... CHECK”.
- **ERRORS**: lists errors detected during the import phase.
- **CHECKS**: indicates the number of elements corresponding to the rows of the Excel file that require verification.
- **FORCE INSERT**: allows data to be forcibly inserted via Excel file and sent to the server through a forced import. Enter “1” in the FORCE INSERT cell to force insertion. If there are no errors but only checks, the key is inserted by forcing its creation.

In the case of errors, retrieve the keys_template.xls file to make necessary corrections and resubmit the import. If all the corrections are error-free, after resubmission to the eCREAM platform following the Import operation, the task result displays the completion level. Specifically, the "Successfully processed elements" field will show the same number of elements as in the "Processed elements" field.

Import keys from file

Import

Insertion task completed

Processed elements : **1**

Successfully processed elements : **1**

Elements to be verified : **0**

Incorrect elements: **0**

[Delete task](#)

Before uploading the file, make sure to have the right template and to have filled it out correctly.

[Download template](#)

Figure 24 – Add key – Mass input – Import keys from file

When downloading the "task_results.xls" file again, the columns indicating the import outcome will be populated with the following values:

STATUS	ERRORS	CHECKS
OK		

Using the "Delete task" button, the user can delete the file corresponding to the import attempt. From the import task page, the user can view the execution of tasks. If any tasks are running, the Admin user can stop them and then delete them.

4.4.1.3 Tasks

The "Tasks" menu item allows the user to monitor the progress of imports. The main flow to reach the "Tasks" function is described below:

1. The operator authenticates in the TM system through the provided credentials as an Admin.
2. The system opens the TM interface, and the menu is displayed.
3. The operator accesses the "Add key" menu item.
4. The KM selects the "Tasks" feature.
5. The operator can perform the desired operations on the "Tasks" page.

By selecting the "Tasks" item, the Import tasks interface appears, displaying the following columns:

- Import date: the date on which the import attempt was made.
- Task ID: the identifier of the import task.
- Application: the name of the eCREAM application for which the import attempt was made.

- Total elements: the number of elements corresponding to the rows in the excel file that were imported or attempted to be imported.
- Added: the number of elements corresponding to the rows of the excel file that were successfully added.
- Existing: the number of elements in the task corresponding to the rows of the excel file that elements already existed.
- In errors: the number of elements corresponding to the rows of the excel file that encountered errors during the import phase.
- To check: the number of elements corresponding to the rows of the excel file that must undergo the check phase.
- Actions: these are the actions that can be performed, including "Download result" with the download symbol, and "Delete task" with the trash symbol.

+ Add key
⚙ Manage keys
🌐 Translate
Riccardo Rossi

Import Tasks [Refresh](#)

Import data	Task ID	Application	Total elements	Added	Existing	In errors	To check	Actions
12/02/2024	80	ED EHR	1	1	0	0	0	
12/02/2024	74	ED EHR	1	0	0	1	0	
05/02/2024	73	ED EHR	2	1	0	0	1	
05/02/2024	72	ED EHR	2	0	0	2	0	
30/01/2024	71	ED EHR	1	0	0	0	1	
30/01/2024	70	ED EHR	1	0	0	1	0	
30/01/2024	69	ED EHR	1	0	0	1	0	

Figure 25 – Add key – Import Tasks

Specifically, by clicking on the 'Download result' button, you can download the 'task_result.xls' file and review the import results to understand any errors and make the necessary corrections for successful data loading. Conversely, by clicking on the 'Delete task' button, you can delete the file corresponding to the import attempt.

4.2 MANAGE KEYS tabs

A user with the ADMIN application role can access the "Manage keys" menu item to perform the following operations:

- Verify the existence of a key already present as a result of an entry request to the Key Manager.
- Modify a key attribute.

The main flow to reach the "Manage keys" functional page is described below:

1. The operator authenticates in the TM system using the provided Admin credentials.
2. The system opens the TM interface, based on the authenticated role, and the menu is displayed.
3. The Admin operator accesses the "Manage keys" menu item.
4. The operator can proceed with the desired operations on the "Manage keys" page.

Application	Keys(#)	Values(#)	Italian	Slovenian	Slovak	Polish	Greek
ED EHR	21	26	34%	7%	3%	3%	3%
Dashboard	11	14	35%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Citizens mobile app	4	4	100%	25%	25%	0%	0%
Statistical analysis platform	3	4	25%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Citizens backend Service	25	27	85%	29%	3%	0%	3%

Figure 26 – Manage keys menu

Once logged into the "Manage keys" functional page, the user can see:

Code	Full text	Short text	Applications	State	Op.
A1	test onthology	onthology		●	✎ 🗑️
A2	Add			●	✎ 🗑️
BT_NEW	New		ED EHR	●	✎ 🗑️
BT_SAVE	Save		ED EHR	●	✎ 🗑️
Calcium blood	blood calcium result	Ca	ED EHR	●	✎ 🗑️
ec.acceptance.header	Patient reception in the emergency department		Citizens backend Service, Dashboard	●	✎ 🗑️
ec.action.create	Create		Citizens backend Service	●	✎ 🗑️
ec.action.save	Save		Citizens mobile app, Citizens backend Service	●	✎ 🗑️
ec.apporto_calorico	Calorie intake/kg weight		Citizens backend Service, Citizens mobile app, Dashboard	●	✎ 🗑️
ec.brother_symptoms_10_lbl	Cardiac disorder		Citizens backend Service	●	✎ 🗑️

Figure 27 – Manage keys interface

The user can view the list of available keys, organised into the following columns:

- Code: indicates the eCREAM code of the key.
- Full text: provides the full text description of the key.
- Short text: provides the short text description of the key.
- Applications: lists the eCREAM applications associated with the key.
- State: indicates the state of the key.
- Op.: shows the possible operations with two function keys:

- The pencil icon allows editing the selected key.
- The trash can icon allows deleting the key.

To facilitate the search for a key to be edited, the user can use the filtering function described below.

4.2.1 Searching

Once the user accesses the “Manage keys” menu item, they can use the Filter option within the “Manage keys” functional page to search for existing keys. The main flow to reach the "Searching" functionality is described below:

- The operator authenticates in the TM system using the provided Admin credentials.
- The system opens the TM interface, and the menu is displayed.
- The Admin operator accesses the "Manage keys" menu item.
- The operator clicks on the Filter function key and can search for the desired key by filling in the specific filters.

Code	Full text	Short text	Applications	State	Op.
A1	test ontology	ontology		●	
A2	Add			●	
BT_NEW	New		ED EHR	●	
BT_SAVE	Save		ED EHR	●	
ec.acceptance.header	Patient reception in the emergency department		Citizens backend Service, Dashboard	●	
ec.action.create	Create		Citizens backend Service	●	
ec.action.save	Save		Citizens mobile app, Citizens backend Service	●	
ec.apporto_calorico	Calorie intake/kg weight		Citizens backend Service, Citizens mobile app, Dashboard	●	
ec.brother_symptoms_10_lbl	Cardiac disorder		Citizens backend Service	●	
ec.brother_symptoms_11_lbl	Gastrointestinal complaints		Citizens backend Service	●	

Figure 28 – Searching surface

The Admin user accesses the key list page and sets the filter values according to their search needs, by entering one or more of the following values: code, application, module, domain, text, ontology, ontology code, and tags.

Filter

search the keys

Code Application Module

Domain Text

Ontology Ontology code Tags

Search Reset

Figure 29 – Searching Filter

The user can proceed with the search or clear the filters by selecting the "Search" or "Reset" buttons, respectively, as shown below:

Figure 30 – Searching function keys search and reset

After selecting the "Search" button, if there is a key that matches the search criteria, the corresponding keys are displayed on the page. Otherwise, a "Not Found" message is shown.

Code	Full text	Short text	Application	Date	Status
anatomy	anatomy	anatomy			On
all	all				On
EPU01	all		EU-01		On
EPU02	all		EU-02		On
all	all		EU-01		On
all	all		EU-02		On
all	all		EU-03		On
all	all		EU-04		On
all	all		EU-05		On
all	all		EU-06		On
all	all		EU-07		On
all	all		EU-08		On
all	all		EU-09		On
all	all		EU-10		On
all	all		EU-11		On
all	all		EU-12		On
all	all		EU-13		On
all	all		EU-14		On
all	all		EU-15		On
all	all		EU-16		On
all	all		EU-17		On
all	all		EU-18		On
all	all		EU-19		On
all	all		EU-20		On
all	all		EU-21		On
all	all		EU-22		On
all	all		EU-23		On
all	all		EU-24		On
all	all		EU-25		On
all	all		EU-26		On
all	all		EU-27		On
all	all		EU-28		On
all	all		EU-29		On
all	all		EU-30		On

Figure 31 – Searching

In the list of keys responding to the search, the Key Code, full text and short text, and the linked application are displayed. The "Status" and the two buttons, "Edit Key" and "Delete key", are also shown.

4.2.2 Editing key

After accessing the "Manage keys" menu item, the Admin user can search for and edit the entered keys. Using the "Edit key" button, the user can:

- Edit the general data associated with the key.
- Modify the key values concerning temporal validity.
- Manage applications associated with the key.
- Visualise translations.

Below are the steps the admin user must follow to reach the "edit key" function:

1. Authenticate in the TM system using the provided Admin credentials.
2. The system opens the TM interface according to the authenticated role, and the menu is displayed
3. Access the "Manage keys" menu through the "Manage keys" function key.
4. On the key list page, identify a key and select the "Edit" action

5. The “Edit key” form opens, displaying the current values of the key attributes stored in the database. The form is in "editable" mode.
6. Edit the necessary values and confirm the operation using the "Save" button.
7. The system performs validation checks.
8. If all checks pass successfully, the new key and its attributes are stored in the Key DB, and a confirmation message is displayed to the user.
9. If any checks fail, the new key is not stored, and the KMA notifies the user of errors.

Code	Full text	Short text	Applications	State	Op.
A1	test onthology	onthology		●	
A2	Add			●	
BT_NEW	New		ED EHR	●	
BT_SAVE	Save		ED EHR	●	
Calcium blood	blood calcium result	Ca	ED EHR	●	
ec.acceptance.header	Patient reception in the emergency department		Citizens backend Service, Dashboard	●	
ec.action.create	Create		Citizens backend Service	●	
ec.action.save	Save		Citizens mobile app, Citizens backend Service	●	
ec.apporto_calorico	Calorie intake/kg weight		Citizens backend Service, Citizens mobile app, Dashboard	●	
ec.brother_symptoms_10_lbl	Cardiac disorder		Citizens backend Service	●	

Figure 32 – editing key

After clicking the “Edit” button (indicated by the pencil symbol) associated with a chosen key, a new window opens where you can edit the key. In the edit interface, it is possible to override the following fields in the upper section:

- **Domain field** indicates whether the key belongs to the health domain or the SW elements domain, selectable via drop-down menu.
- **Element type**, choose whether it is standard or custom terminology from a drop-down menu.
- **Definition**, provide a description of the key.
- **Tags**, used to categorise and identify the key with the search function.

Additional tags can be added in the specific tag field:

Figure 33 – Tags

In the lower space, you can edit the following fields:

- **Last value:** setting the previous value as full text and short text.
- **Key Values:** setting the previous value with start and end validity date.

- **Applications:** setting the applications with which the key is associated
- **Translations:** checking the translations made.

After making the changes, you can save them using the "Save" button.

Figure 34 - Editing key

4.3 TRANSLATE tab

The admin user can access the "Translate" menu item to check the status of translations for all keys entered into the system or to check the translation of a specific key.

The main flow to reach the "Translate" functionality is described below:

1. The operator authenticates in the TM system using the provided Admin/Translator credentials.
2. The system opens the TM interface based on the authenticated role, and the menu is displayed.
3. The Admin/Translator operator accesses the "Translate" menu item.

Application	Keys (F)	Values (F)	Italian	Slovenian	Slovak	Polish	Greek
ED EHR	24	29	34%	0%	3%	3%	3%
Dashboard	13	16	37%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Citizens mobile app	6	7	57%	14%	14%	0%	0%
Statistical analysis platform	4	5	20%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Citizens backend Service	28	31	63%	23%	3%	0%	3%

Figure 35 - Menu translate

The user with Admin role who accesses the "Translate" menu, visualises the following interface:

Language	Keys	Values	Validated values	Not validated values	Not translated values
Italian	60	69	37	31	1
Slovenian	60	69	10	59	0
Slovak	60	69	2	67	0
Polish	60	69	1	67	1
Greek	60	69	2	67	0

Figure 36 - Translate

In this interface, you can visualise the available languages in the platform and the number of keys and their values:

- in "Green", the number of translated and validated values,
- in "Yellow", the number of translated and not validated values,
- in "Red," the number of untranslated values.

Selecting one of the "Green," "Yellow," or "Red" icons takes you to the page containing the list of translated and validated values, translated and non-validated values, and untranslated values, respectively.

4.3.1 Validated value

The Admin user who selects the "Green" icon enters the page containing the list of translated and validated values.

Key Code	Start date	End date	Definition	Full text	Translated full text	Short text	Translated short text	Op.
1212121				colite uterosa	colite uterosa	colite uterosa	colite uterosa	
1234521				11212112	11212112	333333333333333333333333	333333333333333333333333	
A1				test onthology	test di ontologia	onthology	ontologia	
A2				Add	Aggiungi			
anaemia			a condition in which the number of red blood cells or the haemoglobin concentration within them is lower than normal	anaemia	anemia	anaemia	anemia	
Analysis				analysis	analisi	analysis	analisi	
anamnesis			patient's medical history	Anamnesis	Anamnesi	Anamnesis	Anamnesi	
anastomosis	21/03/2024		a connection made surgically between adjacent blood vessels, parts of the intestine, or other channels of the body	anastomosis	anastomosi	anastomosis	anastomosi	
anastomosis		19/03/2024	a connection made surgically between adjacent blood vessels, parts of the intestine, or other channels of the body	anastomosis	anastomosi	anastomosis	anastomosi	
artery	21/03/2024			artery	arteria	artery	arteria	
BT_NEW			New button	New	Nuovo			

Figure 37 - Translate - Validated value

The translation language and "validation" status of keys and key values are displayed in the upper left.

From this interface it is possible to visualise the list of values that have been translated and validated, or to use the Filter option to search for a specific key.

Key Code	Start date	End date	Definition	Full text	Translated full text	Short text	Translated short text	Op.
1212121				colite ulterosa	colite ulterosa	colite ulterosa	colite ulterosa	
1234521				11212112	11212112	33333333333333333333	33333333333333333333	
A1				test onthology	test di ontologia	onthology	ontologia	
Az				Add	Aggiungi			
anaemia			a condition in which the number of red blood cells or the haemoglobin concentration within them is lower than normal	anaemia	anemia	anaemia	anemia	
Analysis				analysis	analisi	analysis	analisi	
anamnesis			patient's medical history	Anamnesis	Anamnesi	Anamnesis	Anamnesi	
anastomosis	21/03/2024		a connection made surgically between adjacent blood vessels, parts of the intestine, or other channels of the body	anastomosis	anastomosi	anastomosis	anastomosi	
anastomosis		19/03/2024	a connection made surgically between adjacent blood vessels, parts of the intestine, or other channels of the body	anastomosis	anastomosi	anastomosis	anastomosi	
artery	21/03/2024			artery	arteria	artery	arteria	
BT_NEW			New button	New	Nuovo			

Figure 38 - Translate - Filter

Selecting "Filter" opens the detailed search mask where you can set the various criteria.

Figure 39 - Translate - filter

After setting the search criteria, select the "Search" button to perform the search.

To clear the fields and set a new search, select "Reset".

The search results will display all the keys that meet the set criteria. For each key, the following details are visualised:

- Key Code: the unique identifier of the key.
- Start date: the validity start date of the key value
- End date: the end validity date of the key value
- Definition: describes the meaning of the key value
- Full text: the text shown by the eCREAM software in the long text version
- Translated full text: the translated text shown by the eCREAM software in the long text version
- Short text: the text shown by the eCREAM software in the short text version
- Translated short text: the translated text shown by the eCREAM software in the short text version

- Op: is the column that identifies the operations that can be performed, indicated by the appropriate symbol

Key	Date	Short view	Full view	Definition	Full text	Translated full text	Short text	Translated short text	Op
A2					Aggi	Agglungi			✓
EPUB1			View button		View	Visualizza			✓
EPUB16			See a button		See	Visualizza			✓
ASSOCIATION_HEADER			Text placed in the first section of the association form	Header section in the emergency assessment form	Associazioni per assistere nei momenti di emergenza	Associazioni per assistere nei momenti di emergenza			✓
ASSOCIATION_KEY					See	Visualizza			✓
ASSOCIATION_KEY_FULL					Other	Altro			✓
ASSOCIATION			See operation		Operazioni / Functionamenti		See		✓
ASSOCIATION			View Single Item		Visualizza elemento singolo				✓
ASSOCIATION_CONTAINER			Date of association of container		Date di associazione del contenitore				✓
ASSOCIATION_CONTAINER			Date of birth		Date di nascita				✓
ASSOCIATION_CONTAINER			Biological father date of birth		Date di nascita del padre biologico				✓
ASSOCIATION_CONTAINER			Birth to birth		Nascita a nascita				✓
ASSOCIATION_CONTAINER				At least one child present on this date	Uno o più figli presenti in questa data				✓
ASSOCIATION_CONTAINER			Total of therapy nursing care		Therapy care	Tipi di terapia			✓
IMPACT_1			Test impact 1 form title		Impact 1	Impatto numero 1	in	in	✓
IMPACT_16			Button label		See	Visualizza	See	See	✓

Figure 40 - Translate - searching filter

By selecting "edit translation," the following screen appears:

Translate > Validated > A2

Key: **A2**

Domain: Software

Definition: [Text area]

Italian translation

Full Text

Max length: [Text area]

Text: Add [Text area]

Translated Text: Agglungi [Text area]

Short Text

Max length: [Text area]

Text: [Text area]

Translated Text: [Text area]

Figure 41 - Translate - edit translation

In the upper left corner, the language of the translation is displayed.

4.3.2 Not validated value

When the Admin user selects the "Yellow" icon, you enter the page displaying a list of translated but unvalidated values. The translation language and the "not validated" status of keys and key values are displayed in the upper left corner.

From this interface, it is possible to view the list of values that have been translated but not yet validated, or to search for a specific key.

Key Code	Start date	End date	Definition	Full text	Translated full text	Short text	Translated short text	Op.
All				test onthology	test di onthologia	onthology	onthologia	
Calcium blood			Laboratory test	blood calcium result	risultato del calcio nel sangue	Ca	Ca	
ec.brathtr_sypmtoms_10_04				Cardiac disorder	Disturbo cardiaco			
ec.350.view				View Single red item	Visualizza un singolo articolo rosso			
ec.cancel.020				Cancel operation	Annullamento dell'operazione			
ec.drug			Label pagina del trattamento	Treatment	Tattamento			
ec.afh.dementia	30/01/2024		Distasse ...	Cognitive disorder	Disturbo cognitivo	Dementia	Demenza	
ec.afh.dementia	30/01/2024		Distasse ...	Dementia cognitive impairment	Demenza cognitiva	Dementia	Demenza	
ec.emoglobin	03/03/2024		Hemoglobin (haemoglobin)[E] He or hgb in a protein containing iron that facilitates the transport of oxygen in red blood cells. Almost all vertebrates contain hemoglobin, [E] with the exception of the fish family Channichthyidae[E] and the tissues of some invertebrate animals. Hemoglobin in the blood carries oxygen from the respiratory organs (lungs or gills) to the other tissues of the body, where it releases the oxygen to enable aerobic respiration which powers the animal's metabolism. A healthy human has 12 to 20 grams of hemoglobin in every 100 mL of blood. Hemoglobin is a metalloprotein, a chromoprotein, and dialyzin.	Hemoglobin	Emoglobina	HbG	HbG	

Figure 42 - Translate - list of translated and non-validated values

Selecting "Filter" opens the detailed search mask where you can set the various criteria.

Translate - Filter (non-validated)

search the keys

Code: Application: Module:

Domain: Text:

Search Reset

Figure 43 - Translate - Filter (non-validated)

After setting the search criteria, you click the "Search" button to execute the search. To clear the fields and start a new search, you must click "Reset".

The search results display all keys that meet the specified criteria. For each key, the following information is shown:

- Key Code: the unique identifier of the key. The value should be self-explanatory.
- Start date: the start validity date of the key value.
- End date: the end validity date of the key value.
- Definition: describes the meaning of the key value.
- Full text: the text shown by the eCREAM software in the long text version.
- Translated full text: the translated text shown by the eCREAM software in its long text version.
- Short text: the text shown by the eCREAM software in its short text version.
- Translated short text: the translated text shown by the eCREAM software in its short text version.
- Op: this column identifies available operations. The pencil symbol represents editing of the translation ("edit translation"), while the check mark symbol represents validation of the translation.

Op.

Figure 44 - Translate - operations

By selecting "edit translation," the following screen appears:

Figure 45 - Translate - edit translation

In the upper left corner, the language of translation is displayed.

In the main area of the window, the key code is displayed along with associated all fields available for editing and validation.

After making the necessary changes, you can validate the changes by selecting the "Validate" button.

If you only need to validate a translation without making further edits, you can directly select the "Validate" button. The action will return you to the mask displaying the list of translated values that have not yet been validated.

4.3.3 Not translated value

When the Admin user selects the "Red" icon, it is possible to access the page displaying a list of untranslated values.

Key Code	Start date	End date	Definition	Full text	Translated full text	Short text	Translated short text	Op.
TM_INTEGRATION_ERROR			Integration error with deepL API	DeepL integration error	DeepL integration error	Integration error	Integration error	

Figure 46 - Translate - values not translated

In the upper left corner, the translation language and the status of keys labelled as "Not translated" are displayed.

From this interface, it is possible to view the list of values that require translation and validation. Additionally, you can use the Filter feature to search for a specific key that needs to be translated.

Figure 47 - Translate - filter (values not translated)

Selecting "Filter" opens a detailed search mask where various criteria can be set.

After configuring the search criteria, click the "Search" button to execute the search.

To clear the fields and start a new search, click "Reset".

The search results display all keys that meet the specified criteria, showing the following details for each key:

- Key Code: unique identifier of the key.
- Start date: start validity date of the key value.
- End date: end validity date of the key value.
- Definition: description of the key value's meaning.
- Full text: text displayed in the eCREAM software in its long form.
- Translated full text: translated text displayed in the eCREAM software in its long form.
- Short text: text displayed in the eCREAM software, in its short form.
- Translated short text: translated text displayed in the eCREAM software in its short form.
- Op: column indicating available operations; the pencil symbol allows editing of the translation ("edit translation"), while the check mark symbol signifies validation of the translation ("Validate translation").

Figure 48 - Translate - operations

By selecting "edit translation," the following screen appears:

Figure 49 - Translate - edit translation

In the upper left corner, the language of the translation is displayed.

In the main area of the window, the key code is shown along with all the fields being edited.

5. TRANSLATOR USER

The Translator user seeking access to the TM platform should request credentials from the support team and log in via the link translation.ecreamproject.eu.

5.1 ACCESS TO TM PLATFORM

From the login link, you can view the following screen:

Translation Manager

Username*

Password*

 LOGIN

Figure 49 - Access to the TM platform - translator

To access the platform, ensure all required fields are filled: Username and Password, which will serve as your login credentials provided by the support team for the TM platform:

Translation Manager

Username*
admin

Password*
.....

 LOGIN

Figure 50 - TM platform access - credentials

After entering the Username and Password, click on the Login button to access the platform.

5.2 PASSWORD CHANGE OR RECOVERY

To change the password, you need to contact the Support team.

5.3 HOME PLATFORM

When an operator logs in with the role of Translator, the Home screen is displayed as follows:

- Top Left:
 - o the eCREAM logo, which functions as a button to return to the Home screen when navigating within the platform.
- Top-level menu:
 - o the "Translate" function key.
- Top right:
 - o the label displaying the operator's first and last name with a function key for a second-level menu.
- Top center:
 - o the eCREAM project image.
- Center, the Translation Manager table, which includes:
 - Application column: Lists the applications managed in TM.
 - Keys column: displays the number of eCREAM keys associated with each application.
 - Values column: Shows the different values that each key can take in the different applications.
 - Language columns: Displays only the languages assigned to the Translator. Each language column shows the percentage of confirmed translations, indicated by two colours:
 1. Red, when the percentage of translations is not complete
 2. Green, when the percentage of translations is complete

Next to the percentage, for each language and for each application, there is a download symbol. Clicking this allows the user to download the JSON file, which describes the variables and the different values assigned to the key.

The screenshot shows the Home TM - Translator SL - SK interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with a "Translate" button and the user's name "Janez Zelen". Below the navigation bar is a banner with the eCREAM logo and the text "RESEARCH AND ED PRACTICE GET TOGETHER". The main content is a table with the following columns: Application, Keys(#), Values(#), Slovenian, and Slovak. The table contains the following data:

Application	Keys(#)	Values(#)	Slovenian	Slovak
ED EHR	21	26	7% ↓	3% ↓
Dashboard	11	14	0% ↓	0% ↓
Citizens mobile app	4	4	25% ↓	25% ↓
Statistical analysis platform	3	4	0% ↓	0% ↓
Citizens backend Service	25	27	29% ↓	3% ↓

Figure 51 - Home TM – Translator SL - SK

Next to the percentage for each language and each application is the download symbol, allowing you to download the Json file that describes the variables and different values assigned to the key.

```
[
  {
    "key": "action.save",
    "eCreamKey": "ec.action.save",
    "definition": "",
    "values": [
      {
        "fullText": "Salva",
        "shortText": null,
        "startDate": null,
        "endDate": null,
        "fullTextMaxLength": null,
        "shortTextMaxLength": null
      }
    ]
  }
],
```

Figure 52 - Json

Adding a new key automatically compiles the JSON, which can then be downloaded as described above. The downloaded JSON is composed as follows:

- **Key:** Contains the compilation of the key field and must be of type string.
- **eCreamKey:** Contains the eCREAM code of the key and must be of type string.
- **Definition:** Contains the description entered in the "definition" field and must be of type string.
- **Values:** indicates the values assigned to the key, distinguished as:
 - fullText: string
 - shortText: string
 - startDate: date in the format dd/mm/yyyy
 - endDate: date in the format dd/mm/yyyy
 - fullTextMaxLength: integer
 - shortTextMaxLength: integer

5.4 MENU TABS

5.4.1 TRANSLATE tab

The Translator user can access the "Translate" menu item to check the status of translations for all keys entered in the system or to promptly check the translation of a specific key.

The main flow to reach the "Translate" functionality is described below:

1. The operator authenticates in the TM system through the provided credentials as Admin/Translator.
2. The system opens the TM interface, displaying the menu based on the authenticated role.
3. The Admin/Translator operator accesses the "Translate" menu item.

The translation and/or validation of an entered/edited key follows this flow:

+ Add key Manage keys Translate Riccardo Rossi

RESEARCH AND ED PRACTICE **GET TOGETHER**

Application	Keys(†)	Values(†)	Italian	Slovenian	Slovak	Polish	Greek
ED EHR	24	29	34%	8%	8%	8%	8%
Dashboard	13	16	77%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Citizens mobile app	6	7	57%	14%	14%	0%	0%
Statistical analysis platform	4	5	20%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Citizens backend Service	28	31	82%	25%	3%	0%	3%

Figure 53 - Menu translate

The user with Admin role who accesses the "Translate" menu, visualizes the following interface:

+ Add key Manage keys Translate Riccardo Rossi

Language	Keys	Values	Validated values	Not validated values	Not translated values
Italian	60	69	37	31	1
Slovenian	60	69	10	59	0
Slovak	60	69	2	67	0
Polish	60	69	1	67	1
Greek	60	69	2	67	0

Figure 54 - Translate

In this interface you can visualise the languages available in the platform, the number of keys and their values:

- "Green", number of translated and validated values
- "Yellow", the number of translated and not validated values,
- "Red", the number of untranslated values.

Selecting one of the "Green," "Yellow," or "Red" icons takes you to the page containing the list of translated and validated values, translated and non-validated values, and untranslated values, respectively.

5.4.2 Validated value

When the Translator user selects the "Green" icon, it is possible to enter the page containing the list of translated and validated values.

+ Add key * Manage keys 🗨 Translate Riccardo Rossi

Translate > 🇮🇹 Validated

Filter search the keys

Key Code	Start date	End date	Definition	Full text	Translated full text	Short text	Translated short text	Op.
A2				Add	Aggiungi			
BT_NEW			New button	New	Nuovo			
BT_SAVE			Save button	Save	Salva			
ec.acceptance.header			Text placed in the main section of the acceptance form	Patient reception in the emergency department	Accoglienza dei pazienti nel reparto di emergenza			
ec.action.create				Create	Creare			
ec.action.save				Save	Salva			
ec.apporto_calorico				Calorie intake/kg weight	Apporto calorico/kg di peso			
ec.brother_symptoms_11_lbl				Gastrointestinal complaints	Disturbi gastrointestinali			
ec.brother_symptoms_12_lbl				Liver disorders	Disturbi del fegato			

Figure 55 - Translate - Valited value

In the upper left corner, the translation language and the "validation" status of keys and key values are displayed.

From this interface, it is possible to view the list of translated and validated values. You can also use the Filter entry to

search for a specific key punctually.

+ Add key * Manage keys 🗨 Translate Riccardo Rossi

Translate > 🇮🇹 Validated

Filter search the keys

Key Code	Start date	End date	Definition	Full text	Translated full text	Short text	Translated short text	Op.
A2				Add	Aggiungi			
BT_NEW			New button	New	Nuovo			
BT_SAVE			Save button	Save	Salva			
ec.acceptance.header			Text placed in the main section of the acceptance form	Patient reception in the emergency department	Accoglienza dei pazienti nel reparto di emergenza			
ec.action.create				Create	Creare			
ec.action.save				Save	Salva			
ec.apporto_calorico				Calorie intake/kg weight	Apporto calorico/kg di peso			
ec.brother_symptoms_11_lbl				Gastrointestinal complaints	Disturbi gastrointestinali			
ec.brother_symptoms_12_lbl				Liver disorders	Disturbi del fegato			

Figure 56 - Translate - Filter

Selecting "Filter" opens the detail of the search mask in which you can set the various criteria.

Figure 57 - Translate - filter

After setting the search criteria, click the "Search" button to execute the search. To clear the fields and set new search criteria, select "Reset".

The search result will display all keys that meet the specified criteria.

For each key, the following details are shown:

- Key Code: unique identifier of the key.
- Start date: validity start date of the key value
- End date: end validity date of the key value
- Definition: description that explains the meaning of the key value
- Full text: text displayed by the eCREAM software in the long text version
- Translated full text: translated text shown by the eCREAM software, in the long text version
- Short text: text displayed by the eCREAM software, in the short text version
- Translated short text: translated text shown by the eCREAM software, in the short text version
- Op: column that identifies the operations that can be performed. The pencil symbol editing of the translation ("edit translation").

Key Code	Start date	End date	Definition	Full text	Translated full text	Short text	Translated short text	Op
AD				ADD	ADD			
EPUB01			Has button	Has	Has			
EPUB02			Selez button	Selez	Selez			
ASSOCIATION_HEADER			Header section of the association form	Header section of the emergency assessment form	Associazione dei sintomi nei documenti di emergenza (in			
ASSOCIATION				Selez	Selez			
ASSOCIATION_FULL				Other	Other			
ASSOCIATION			Stop connection	Stop connection	Interrompi il collegamento	Stop		
ASSOCIATION			View Single Item	View Single Item	Visualizza elemento singolo			
ASSOCIATION_CONTAINER			Date of association of container	Date of association of container	Date di associazione dei contenitori			
ASSOCIATION_CONTAINER			Date of birth	Date of birth	Date di nascita			
ASSOCIATION_CONTAINER			Biological father date of birth	Biological father date of birth	Date di nascita del padre biologico			
ASSOCIATION_CONTAINER			Birth in hospital	Birth in hospital	Nascita in ospedale			
ASSOCIATION_CONTAINER			At therapy or check present on the date	At therapy or check present on the date	Una terapia o check presente in questa data			
ASSOCIATION_CONTAINER			Title of therapy tracking card	Therapy card	Titolo di terapia			
IMPACT_1			Year impact 1 from file	Impact 1	Impatto anno 1	in	in	
IMPACT_2			Year impact 2 from file	Selez	Selez	Selez	Selez	

Figure 58 - Translate - searching filter

By selecting "edit translation," the following screen appears:

+ Add key Manage keys Translate Riccardo Rossi

Translate > Validated > A2

Key: **A2**

Domain: Software

Definition:

Italian translation

Full Text

Max length:

Text: Add

Translated Text: Agglungi

Short Text

Max length:

Text:

Translated Text:

Figure 59 - Translate - edit translation

In the upper left corner, the language of the translation is displayed.

In the main area of the window, you will see the key code along with all the fields being edited.

5.4.3 Not validated value

When the Admin user clicks the "Yellow" icon, they enter the page containing the list of translated and unvalidated values. The translation language and the "not validated" status of keys and key values are displayed in the upper left corner.

From this interface, it is possible to visualise the list of values that have been translated but have not yet been validated or by entering the Filter entry search for a specific key punctually.

+ Add key Manage keys Translate Riccardo Rossi

Translate > To be validated

Filter search the keys

Key Code	Start date	End date	Definition	Full text	Translated full text	Short text	Translated short text	Op.
A1				test oncologia	test di oncologia	oncologia	oncologia	
Calcium blood			Laboratory test	blood calcium result	risultato del calcio nel sangue	Ca	Ca	
ec.breast_symptoms_30_39				Cardiac disorder	Disturbo cardiaco			
ec.bth.view				View single red item	Visualizza un singolo articolo rosso			
ec.cancel.btn				Cancel operation	Annullamento dell'operazione			
ec.drug			Label pagina dei trattamenti	Treatment	Tattamento			
ec.ahs.dementia	30/01/2024		Disease	Cognitive disorder	Disturbo cognitivo	Dementia	Demenza	
ec.ahs.dementia	30/01/2024		Disease	Dementia cognitive impairment	Demenza cognitiva	Dementia	Demenza	
ec.emoglobin	03/03/2024		Hemoglobin (haemoglobin) Hb or Hgb is a protein containing iron that facilitates the transport of oxygen in red blood cells. Almost all vertebrates contain hemoglobin, [2] with the exception of the fish family Channichthyidae and the tissues of some invertebrate animals. Hemoglobin in the blood carries oxygen from the respiratory organs (lungs or gills) to other tissues of the body, where it releases the oxygen to enable aerobic respiration which powers the animal's metabolism. A healthy human has 12 to 20 grams of hemoglobin in every 100 mL of blood. Hemoglobin is a metalloprotein, a chromoprotein, and a dialysis.	Hemoglobin	Emoglobina	HbG	HbG	

Figure 60 - Translate - list of translated and non-validated values

Selecting "Filter" opens the detail of the search mask in which you can set the various criteria.

Figure 61 - Translate - Filter (not validated)

After setting the search criteria, click the "Search" button to execute the search. To clear the fields and set a new search, select "Reset".

The search result will display all keys that meet the specified criteria. For each key, the following details are shown:

- Key Code: unique identifier of the key. The value should be self-explanatory.
- Start date: validity start date of the key value
- End date: end validity date of the key value
- Definition: description the meaning of the key value
- Full text: text displayed by the eCREAM software, in the long text version
- Translated full text: translated text shown by the eCREAM software, in the long text version
- Short text: text displayed by the eCREAM software, in the short text version
- Translated short text: translated text shown by the eCREAM software, in the short text version
- Op: column identifying operations that can be performed. The pencil symbol allows editing of the translation ("edit translation").

Figure 62 - Translate - operations

By selecting "edit translation," the following screen appears:

Figure 63 - Translate - edit translation

In the upper left corner, the language of the translation is displayed.

In the main area of the window, you will see the key code along with all the fields being edited.

After making the necessary changes, you can validate the changes by selecting the "Validate" button.

In case you only need to validate a translation, you can validate by directly selecting the "Validate" button. You will then return to the interface with the list of values that have been translated but have not yet been validated.

5.4.4 Not translated value

When the Translator user clicks the "Red" icon, they enter the page containing the list of untranslated values.

Figure 64 - Translate - not translated values

The translation language and the "Not translated" status of the keys are displayed in the upper left corner.

From this interface, you can view the list of values that need to be translated and validated; additionally, you can use the Filter option to search specifically for a key that needs translation.

Figure 65 - Translate - filter (not translated values)

Clicking "Filter" opens the detail of the search mask in which you can set the various criteria.

Once you have set the search criteria, click on the "Search" button to initiate the search.

To clear the fields and start a new search, click "Reset".

The search results display all keys that match the specified criteria. For each key, the following details are shown:

- Key Code: unique identifier of the key.
- Start date: start validity date of the key value
- End date: end validity date of the key value
- Definition: description of the meaning of the key value
- Full text: the text shown by the eCREAM software, in the long text version
- Translated full text: translated text shown by the eCREAM software, in the long text version
- Short text: text shown by the eCREAM software, in the short text version
- Translated short text: translated text shown by the eCREAM software, in the short text version
- Op: column that identifies the available operations for each key. The pencil symbol is used to "edit translation", the tick symbol is used to represent validation on the translation ("Validate translation").

Figure 66 - Translate - operations

By selecting "edit translation," the following screen appears:

+ Add key Manage keys Translate Riccardo Rossi

Translate > Not translated > TM_INTEGRATION_ERROR

Key: **TM_INTEGRATION_ERROR**

Domain
Software

Definition
Integration error with deepL aPI

Validate

Italian translation

Full Text	Short Text
Max length	Max length
Text DeepL integration error	Text Integration error
Translated Text DeepL integration error	Translated Text Integration error

Figure 67 - Translate - edit translation

In the upper left corner, the language of the translation is displayed.

In the main area of the window, the key code is associated with all the fields being edited.